

ICSuSaT-2022

5th International Conference on Sustainable Sciences and Technology

Istanbul-TURKEY

01-03 July 2022

ABSTRACT

BOOK

EDITORs

Prof.Dr. İskender AKKURT

Dr. Kadir GÜNOĞLU

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<https://icsusat.net/icsusat-2022>

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SCIENTIFIC PROGRAMME FOR ICSuSaT-2022

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

02 July 2022-Saturday

10.00-12.00	Opening : Prof. Dr. Iskender AKKURT (Chair of ICSuSaT-2022)—Suleyman Demirel University, Isparta / TURKIYE
	Session Chair : Dr. Feride KULALI-- Uskudar University, Istanbul / TURKIYE
	Invited Speaker 1: Prof. Dr. Amir HUSSAIN -- Centre of AI and Robotics, Edinburgh Napier University, Scotland, UK; “Transformative Artificial Intelligence Technologies for Sustainable Healthcare”
	Invited Speaker 2: Prof. Dr. Zakaria BOUMERZOUG -- University of Biskra -Algeria “Recent Advances in the Metallurgical Challenges of Welding Dissimilar ” Invited Speaker 3: Dr. Soumi DUTTA-- Institute of Engineering & Management (IEM), INDIA “Social Network Data Analytics ” Invited Speaker 4: Prof.Dr. Baba Bin Musta--Universiti Malaysia Sabah, Malaysia “Engineering Properties and Mineralogical Identification of Clay Soil from Trusmadi Formation in Bundu Tuhan, Sabah” Invited Speaker 5: Prof.Dr. Josu Takala-- University of Vaasa, Finland “Sustainable Decision Making basing on Science and Technology”
12.00-13.30	BREAK-LUNCH

Session Chair : Dr. Feride KULALI-- Uskudar University, Istanbul / TURKIYE		
58	Tuna Baskoy-- Toronto Metropolitan Univ.-Canada	European Union (EU) Hydrogen Energy Policy and Auto Industry
51	Meleq Bahtijari and Gazmend Nafezi <i>University of Prishtina-Kosova</i>	A systematic study: Different factors of radon exposure in workplaces in Kosovo
5	Dr. Salim Saleh and Mrahmed Khuder <i>Al Hadba University College-Iraq</i>	Optimizing welding parameters with GRA method and inferring a reliable welding process
73	Talha Demirci , Nihat Akın— <i>Selçuk Univ. Konya, Turkiye</i>	Bacteriocin-like activity of some lactic acid bacteria isolated from artisanal hardaliye pickle
29	Suraya Sintang , Mohd Nazmi Mohd Khalli and Assis Kamu---- <i>Universiti Malaysia Sabah-Malaysia</i>	Constructing Socio-Religious Harmony Framework in Sabah, Malaysia Using Fuzzy Delphi Method Analysis
30	Farhana Begum , Md Insiat Islam Rabby, Prof. Dr Syed Zabid Hossain and Prof. Dr. Md Ayub Ali-- <i>Ministry of education, Bangladesh</i>	Influencing Factors for Environmental Sustainability Practices of SMEs: A Systematic Review
32	Rukshana Begum , Farhana Begum, Tohidur Rahman, Syed Nazmul Huda and Nazmul Ahsan Murad-- <i>University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh</i>	Liquidity Management Practices of Private Commercial Banks in Bangladesh for Sustainable Development

13.30-16.30	50	Gazmend Nafezi , Meleq Bahtijari and Rilinde Doli-- <i>University of Prishtina, Kosova</i>	A comparative and systematic study: A review of radon exposure situation in Kosovo
	40	Aykut Yozukmaz and Nurçin Killi— <i>Mugla Sıtkı KoçmanUn. Mugla,Turkiye</i>	First evidence of microplastics in Moon jelly (<i>Aurelia aurita</i> , Linnaeus, 1758); a preliminary study from Gökova Bay (Southern Turkey)
	42	Radwan Al-Dwairi -- <i>Yarmouk University, Jordan</i>	Using social media as an important channel for business companies to achieve customer's satisfaction, loyalty and trust
	43	İrem Yıldırım, Birkay Tosun , Ecem Güner and Zehra Kamışlı Öztürk— <i>Eskişehir Teknik Univ. Turkiye</i>	Geçirimsiz yüzeylerden yağmur suyu hasadı üzerine optimizasyon çalışması
	28	Taner Kavas and Ayşegül Peynircioğlu— <i>Afyonkocatepe Univ. Turkiye</i>	Investigation of the electromagnetic shielding properties of fabric coated with polymers
	47	Pr. Dr. Fatima Benrachi and Dr. Nadjat Laouet-- <i>University Frères Mentouri Constantine 1, Algeria</i>	Nuclear structure investigation of even-even proton rich nuclei in vicinity of rp-process path
	52	Nadjet Laouet , Fatima Benrachi and Akram Bouguerra-- <i>University Frères Mentouri Constantine 1, Algeria</i>	A=96 proton rich nuclei and Gamow-Teller decay properties
	56	Amal Ait El Djoudi , Abdelkader Cheddad and Faiza Remdani— <i>Lab. de Physique des Particules et Physique Statistique, Ecole Normale Supérieure-Kouba, Algeria</i>	Influence of some Parameters on the QCD Phase Diagram within the MIT Bag Model
	49	Gamze Can and Zeliha Ergul Aydin-- <i>Eskisehir Technical University, Turkiye</i>	Personalized Daily Tour Planning with Mixed-integer Programming
	25	Abdelkrim Khired and S. Zitouni-- <i>Electrical engineering Laboratory, University of Bejaia, Algeria</i>	Capacity Analysis for Urban Area Scenario for Long Term Evolution--Advanced with Wireless Network Service
	60	Mohammed Awad and Abedelkareem Zidan-- <i>Arab American University, Palestine</i>	Prediction of Compressive Strength of Concrete in Palestinian Using Machine Learning Techniques
	75	Seher Arslankaya -- <i>Sakarya University,Industrial Engineering Department, Sakarya- Turkiye</i>	Demand Forecasting with Simple Linear Regression, Multiple Linear Regression and Artificial Neural Networks in a Gas Distribution Company
	76	Seher Arslankaya -- <i>Sakarya University,Industrial Engineering Department, Sakarya- Turkiye</i>	Prediction of Electricity Demand in Turkey with Artificial Neural Networks and Interface Development with Python
16.30-16.45	BREAK		
16.45-19.00	68	Cem Akıllı , Zuhul Er- <i>Istanbul Technical Univ.Turkiye</i>	A study of smart ports by cargo handling in Antwerp port
	65	Burak Kişinn , Hakan Ertürk, Tahsin Engin, İmdat Vural, Zeki Tosun, Murat Can Yılmaz and Abdurrahman Alper Özalp-- <i>Bursa Uludağ Üniversitesi, Turkiye</i>	Mikro Kanal Akışına Sahip Evaporatörün Yenilikçi R1234yf Gazı ile Farklı Operatif Şartlar ve Kanal Uzunluklarında Faz Dönüşümü Mekanizmasının Nümerik İncelenmesi
	57	Hanane Saifi and Fatima Benrachi-- <i>Univeristé Frères Mentouri, Algeria</i>	Single particle evolution along N=51 isotones
	44	Uğurcan Uzunkaya , Şimal Uzgur, İrem Top and Zehra Kamışlı Öztürk-- <i>Eskişehir Technical Univ., Turkiye</i>	Decision Support System Design for Energy Efficient Home Management
	35	Abdullateef Jadallah , Suraa Hassan and Ghassan Bilal-- <i>Tikrit University, Iraq</i>	Design and Performance Analysis of a Smart Greenhouse Powered By a Controlled Solar Energy System
	7	Prof. Yabka Assia , C. Yasmina Amrane, H. Bahia, Leila Boudine and N.Baba-- <i>Medical school of Algiers. Algeria</i>	The Graphics tablet and its contribution to Anatomy Teaching

3	Prof. Dr Selena Samardžić , L. Lekić, B. Munjiza, A. Sitarević, Dr Robert Lakatoš, Prof. Dr Uranija Kozmidis Luburić and Prof. Dr Ivana Lončarević-- <i>Faculty of technical sciences, Serbia</i>	Assessment of adverse effects of background noise on employees in a Call center
37	Sanja Rackov , Milan Vranes and Branka Pilic-- <i>University of Novi Sad, Serbia</i>	Preparation and Long-Term Stabilization of Electrospun Polysaccharide Nanofiber Membranes as a Potential for Biomaterials
4	Jelena Lubura , Predrag Kojić, Jelena Pavličević, Bojana Ikonić and Oskar Bera-- <i>University of Novi Sad, Serbia</i>	Prediction of the natural rubber mechanical properties using machine learning
8	Prof. Yabka Assia , Hamzaoui Bahia, Chafika Yasmina Amrane and Leila Boudine-- <i>Medical school of Algeria</i>	Review of the literature on the probable causes of lateral ankle sprain
39	Jelena Tanasic , Tamara Erceg, Ivan Krakovsky, Ljiljana Tanasic and Ivan Ristic-- <i>University of Novi Sad, Serbia</i>	Swelling properties of polyurethane hydrogels
61	Hazem Khanfar , Shorooq Mhdawi, Muayad Abu Saa and Atef Qasrawi-- <i>Arab American Univ., Palestine</i>	Design and characterization of Tungsten trioxide devices
9	Prof. Yabka Assia , Chafika Yasmina Amrane, H. Bahia, L. Boudine and N. Baba-- <i>Medical school of Algiers, Algeria</i>	The museum of the anatomy laboratory of Algiers
6	Prof. Yabka Assia , Hamzaoui Bahia and Chafika Amrane-- <i>Medical school of Algiers, Algeria</i>	Anatomical pathways of nociception

03 July 2022-Sunday

Session Chair : Dr. Osman GÜNAY —İstanbul Okan University, Istanbul / TURKIYE		
19	Hamzaoui Bahia , Pr Yabka Assia and Chafika Yasmina Amrane-- <i>Medical School, Algeria</i>	Macroscopic and morphometric study of the hypothenar muscle arch
15	Chafika Yasmina Amrane , Dr Maya Bendjelloul, Pr Yabka Assia and Pr Hamzaoui Bahia-- <i>University Hospital Center of Constantine, Algeria</i>	The arch of the great saphenous vein (GSV) and its practical value in varicose vein surgery
21	Sabah Hanachi , Karima Sifi, Fatima Zohra Madoui, Salima Zekri and Nouredine Abadi-- <i>Salah Boubnider University Constantine 3, Algeria</i>	The C677T of the MTHFR gene and the risk of schizophrenia in a population of Eastern Algeria
16	Prof. Yabka Assia , Hamzaoui Bahia and Chafika Yasmina Amrane-- <i>Medical school of Algiers, Algeria</i>	Acupuncture, between myth and reality. A review of the literature
17	Hamzaoui Bahia , Pr Yabka Assia and Amrane Chafika-- <i>Medical School, Algeria</i>	Macroscopic and morphometric study of the Berrettini anastomosis
18	Hamzaoui Bahia , Chafika Yasmina Amrane and Pr Yabka Assia-- <i>Medical School, Algeria</i>	Anatomo-clinical study of the ulnar canal at the wrist
67	Yusuf Ceylan , Kadir Gunoğlu, İskender Akkurt— <i>Selçuk University, Konya-Turkiye</i>	Radiation dose Parameters for Environmental sample

09.30-12.30	10	Karima Sifi , Sabah Hanachi, Fatima Madoui, Salima Zekri, Hadia Ziada, Karima Benembarek and Nordine Abadi-- <i>University Salah Bounnider Constantine3, Algeria</i>	Angiotensin Converting Enzyme (ACE) Gene Insertion/Deletion Polymorphism and susceptibility to schizophrenia: A case-control study
	11	Ouardia Zekri — <i>USTHB, Algeria</i>	Catalytic activity of Co/HMS in the conversion of p-nitrophenol to p-aminophenol
	12	Zekri Salima , S. Hanachi, K. Sifi, K. Benmebarek and N. Abadi-- <i>University Salah Bounnider Constantine3, Algeria</i>	Prostate Cancer: The PSA Marker will soon be replaced
	13	Chafika Yasmina Amrane , Yabka Assia, Pr Hamzaoui Bahia and Dr Maya Bendjelloul-- <i>University Hospital Center of Constantine, Algeria</i>	Highlighting Salmon's artery (fixing artery of the arch of the inferior thyroid artery) about a case.
	14	Chafika Yasmina Amrane , Pr Hamzaoui Bahia, Pr Yabka Assia and Dr Maya Bendjelloul-- <i>University Hospital Center of Constantine, Algeria</i>	The fine caliber of the inferior laryngeal nerve can be a source of iatrogenic lesion
	69	Osman Gunay , Kadir Gunoglu, İskender Akkurt — <i>Yildiz Technical University, Istanbul-Turkiye</i>	Radium equivalent dose from Natural Radiation Measurement
	20	Hamzaoui Bahia , Pr Yabka Assia and Chafika Yasmina Amrane-- <i>Medical School, Algeria</i>	Compression of the deep terminal branch of the ulnar nerve: a case report
	38	Kadir Gunoglu, Osman Günay , İskender Akkurt— <i>Yildiz Technical University, Istanbul-Turkiye</i>	⁴⁰ K natural radioactivity for sand samples.
	48	Raffles Sinaga , Yana Taryana, Lisman Suryanegara and Yudi Darma-- <i>Bandung Institute of Tech, Indonesia</i>	Effective microwave absorption in X band of lightweight, robust, and flexible cellulose nanofibers composites
	64	Pelin Kanar , Asli Beyza Ciftpinar and Zeynep Idil Erzurum Cicek-- <i>Eskisehir Technical Univ., Turkiye</i>	Ensemble learning based machine learning models for predictive maintenance
	59	Gülnur Ergüner , İskender Akkurt, Atilla Evcin, Kadir Gunoglu— <i>Suleyman Demirel Univ., Isparta-Turkiye</i>	Radiation Shielding test of PbO added composite
	41	Hrithik Rana and Ashish Kumar Sinha -- <i>Galgotias University, India</i>	Image classification using CNN
	70	Kadir Gunoglu , Hakan Akyıldırım, İskender Akkurt— <i>Isparta Applied Science University, Isparta-Turkiye</i>	Monte Carlo Approaches for radiation shielding
12.30-13.30	BREAK - LUNCH		
13.30-17.00	63	M Harunur Rashid , Nazmul Hassan Ohe and Md. Khalid Shaifullah Shuvro-- <i>Khulna Univ. of Engin. & Technology, Bangladesh</i>	Ferrocement Wall Panel Performance Under Elevated temperature
	66	Kerem Dızman , K. Mutlu, D. Dağdelen, S. Çalıřkan and S. Hartomaciođlu-- <i>Nexans Turkiye End. Ve Tic. A.ř., Turkiye</i>	Optimization of Process Parameters of Local Area Network (LAN) Cables
	22	Khalida Boudaoud — <i>Univ. Salah Bounnider, Algeria</i>	Acute pancreatitis and diabetes mellitus : A cause and effect loop
	23	Mohammed Ouali and Rabah Magraoui-- <i>University, Blida, Algeria</i>	Predictive Maintenance of Rotating Machines Industrial application and proposal of technological solutions
	24	Rabah Magraoui and Mohammed Ouali-- <i>University, Blida, Algeria</i>	Influence of faults on the dynamic behavior of a rotating system. Application to an industrial machine and proposal of technological solutions
	31	Amina Boukerma, Karima Sifi and Aya Boufamma-- <i>University Hospital Center, Algeria</i>	A comparative study of serum creatinine dosage on two different automats: Dimension® EXL™ 200 and Architect ci 8200
	33	Sérine Madji , Mohamed Belmedani, Elhadj Mekatel and Asma Hemmi-- <i>USTHB, Algeria</i>	The removal of azo dye on ZnO/clay heterosystem by photocatalysis

	34	Asma Hemmi , Mohamed Belmedani, Elhadj Mekatel and Sérine Madj-- <i>USTHB, Algeria</i>	Azo-dyes photocatalytic degradation in aqueous suspension of ZnO under solar irradiation
	71	Kadir Gunoglu , Semsettin Kılınçarslan, Yasemin Şimşek, İskender Akkurt— <i>Isparta Applied Science Univ. Isparta-Türkiye</i>	How much radiation may be shielded by a Wood ?
	45	Merai Soundous , Benrachi Fatima and Laouet Nadjet-- <i>Frères Mentouri Constantine-1 Univ., Algeria</i>	The radiation therapy importance in breast cancer
	46	Esmâ Saadi , Fatima Benrachi and Maryvonne De Jesus— <i>Univ.Frères Mentouri Constantine 1, Algeria</i>	Evaluation of Natural Radioactivity Levels and Potential Radiological Risks of Granite Samples Used in Algerian Dwellings
	53	Pr. Dr. Fatima Benrachi and Dr. Nadjet Laouet— <i>Univ.Frères Mentouri Constantine 1, Algeria</i>	b+ decay nuclear properties of A=80 isobars
	54	Nadjet Laouet , Fatima Benrachi and Akram Bouguerra— <i>Univ.Frères Mentouri Constantine 1, Algeria</i>	B+ decay of A=97 proton rich isobars in 100Sn mass region
	55	Fatima Zohra Chemingui and Fatima Bemrachi— <i>Univ.Frères Mentouri Constantine 1, Algeria</i>	Dosimetric study in radiationtherapy (prostate cancer treatment)
	62	Fatih Biryân , Kenan Koran, Kadir Demirelli and Ahmet Orhan Görgülü— <i>Firat Univ.,Elazığ,Türkiye</i>	Synthesis, characterizations and electrical properties of novel azo-chalcone derivative
	2	Lakhdar Sek -- <i>University of biskra-Algeria</i>	Treatment of Dirac oscillator in Noncommutative geometry
	26	Faci Youcef , Mebtouche Ahmed and Maalem Badredine— <i>CRTI, Algeria</i>	Composite joint damage analysis by digital image correlation
	36	Mohd Khalizan Sabullah , Noreen Nordin and Rahmath Abdulla- <i>Universiti Malaysia Sabah, Malaysia</i>	Early detection for insecticides biomonitoring on vegetables via acetylcholinesterase from the brain tissue of diodon hystrix.
	72	Feride Kulah Özdek , Caner Yalçın-- <i>Uskudar University, Istanbul-Türkiye</i>	Estimation of the effective dose from radon inhalation in thermal spas located in southeast Marmara
	74	İbrahim Çalışkan , İskender Akkurt— <i>Suleyman Demirel University, Istanbul-Türkiye</i>	Radyoterapide kullanılan aSi elektronik portal görüntüleme sisteminin invivo dozimetri için performans degerlendirmesi

ZOOM INFO

02 July 2022-Saturday	
Opening: Prof. Dr. Iskender AKKURT (Chairman)	Topic: ICSuSaT-2022--- opening+invited Jul 2, 2022 09:30 AM Istanbul Join Zoom Meeting https://us06web.zoom.us/j/6319935466?pwd=NzBaSkwzVlcrSUUpWTVpiWGwzMUJsZz09 Meeting ID: 631 993 5466 Passcode: icsusat22
12.00-13.30 LUNCH BREAK	
Saturday Session 2 13:30-16:30 Chair: Dr. Ferie Kulal	Topic: ICSuSaT-22--Session 2 Time: Jul 2, 2022 01:30 PM Istanbul Join Zoom Meeting https://us06web.zoom.us/j/6319935466?pwd=NzBaSkwzVlcrSUUpWTVpiWGwzMUJsZz09 Meeting ID: 631 993 5466 Passcode: icsusat22
16.30- 16.45 BREAK	
Saturday Session 3 16.45- 19.00 Chair: Dr. Feride Kulal	Topic: ICSuSaT-22-session 3 Time: Jul 2, 2022 04:30 PM Istanbul Join Zoom Meeting https://us02web.zoom.us/j/6319935466?pwd=Y29HUW0vcE9lVUtSZCtNYWJ6dVZhZz09 Meeting ID: 631 993 5466 Passcode: icsusat22

03 July 2022-Sunday

Sunday Session 4 09:30-12:30 Chair: Dr	Topic: ICSuSaT-22--Session 4 Time: Jul 3, 2022 09:30 AM Istanbul Join Zoom Meeting https://us06web.zoom.us/j/6319935466?pwd=NzBaSkwzVlcrSUpWTVpiWGwzMUJsZz09 Meeting ID: 631 993 5466 Passcode: icsusat22
	12.00-13.30 LUNCH BREAK
Sunday Session 5 13:30-16:30 Chair: Dr	Topic: ICSuSaT-22--Session 5 Time: Jul 3, 2022 09:30 AM Istanbul Join Zoom Meeting https://us06web.zoom.us/j/6319935466?pwd=NzBaSkwzVlcrSUpWTVpiWGwzMUJsZz09 Meeting ID: 631 993 5466 Passcode: icsusat22

ORAL PRESENTATIONS IN ICSuSaT-2022

Abs.#	Authors	Title	Pages
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74	Ibrahim Çobanbaş, Iskender Akkurt	Radyoterapide kullanılan a-Si elektronik portal görüntüleme sisteminin in-vivo dozimetri için performans Değerlendirmesi	24
2	Lakhdar Sek	treatment of Dirac oscillator in Noncommutative geometry	25
3	Selena Samardžić, Ljubinka Lekić, Biljana Munjiza, Aleksandra Sitarević, Robert Lakatoš, Uranija Kozmidis Luburić Ivana Lončarević	Assessment of adverse effects of background noise on employees in a Call center	26
4	Jelena Lubura, Predrag Kojić, Jelena Pavličević, Bojana Ikonić and Oskar Bera	Prediction of the natural rubber mechanical properties using machine learning	27
5	Drsalim Saleh and Mrahmed Khuder	Optimizing welding parameters with GRA method and inferring a reliable welding process	28
6	Pr Yabka Assia, Hamzaoui Bahia and Chafika Amrane	Anatomical pathways of nociception	29
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9	Yabka Assia, Chafika Yasmina Amrane, Hamzaoui Bahia, Leila Boudine and Naima Baba	The museum of the anatomy laboratory of Algiers	32
10	Karima Sifi, Sabah Hanachi, Fatima Madoui, Salima Zekri, Hadia Ziada, Karima Benembarek and Nordine Abadi	Angiotensin Converting Enzyme (ACE) Gene Insertion/Deletion Polymorphism and susceptibility to schizophrenia: A case-control study	33
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13	Chafika Yasmina Amrane, Yabka Assia, Hamzaoui Bahia and Maya Bendjelloul	Title: Highlighting Salmon's artery (fixing artery of the arch of the inferior thyroid artery) about a case.	36
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15	Chafika Yasmina Amrane, Maya Bendjelloul, Yabka Assia and Hamzaoui Bahia	The arch of the great saphenous vein (GSV) and its practical value in varicose vein surgery	38
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44	Uğurcan Uzunkaya, Şimal Uzgur, İrem Top, Zehra Kamışlı Öztürk	Decision Support System Design for Energy Efficient Home Management	66
45	Merai Soundous, Benrachi Fatima and Laouet Nadjet	The radiation therapy importance in breast cancer	67
46	Esmâ Saadi, Fatima Benrachi and Maryvonne De Jesus	Evaluation of Natural Radioactivity Levels and Potential Radiological Risks of Granite Samples Used in Algerian Dwellings	68
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FOREWORD

Dear Colleagues,

I am pleased to host you all in “**5th International Conference on Sustainable Sciences and Technology (ICSuSaT 2022)**”. The conference has been taken place in the period of 01-03 July, 2022 in İstanbul-Turkiye (and also using ZOOM platform). The ICSuSaT 2022 provided excellent international forum and covers highlights about new results in the wide spectrum of categories from social and sciences. The participants had the opportunity to take part in the presentation of plenary lectures, contributed papers of both oral and poster session types, and of their scientific discussions. There are 5 different theme in ICSuSaT 2022 as detailed below;

- Theme 1.** Sustainable Natural Science
- Theme 2.** Sustainable Social Sciences
- Theme 3.** Sustainable Engineering Sciences
- Theme 4.** Sustainable Applied Sciences
- Theme 5.** Sustainable Medical Sciences

Prof. Dr. İskender AKKURT
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INVITED SPEAKERS

Transformative Artificial Intelligence Technologies for Sustainable Healthcare

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ABSTRACT

Human health and thus healthcare system is important. Thus researchers focused on this issue and new methods are under development for this purposes. In this work, Transformative Artificial Intelligence Technologies for Sustainable Healthcare will be detailed.

Keywords: *Transformative Artificial Intelligence Technologies, Sustainable Healthcare, ANN*

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Recent Advances in the Metallurgical Challenges of Welding Dissimilar

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ABSTRACT

In modern industry, the joining of various materials with different functions or properties is very efficient to make products with high performance, low production and operating costs. Welding dissimilar metals has several applications in industrial construction and manufacturing. The different metal joining processes are divided into three categories, fusion welding, low dilution welding and solid state welding. Fusion welding processes include various arc welding (shielded metal arc, gas arc, submerged arc, flux cored arc and tungsten welding) and spot welding resistance. Low dilution welding includes electron beam welding, laser welding and pulsed arc welding. Solid state welding includes friction welding (rotational friction welding, friction stir welding, linear friction welding), explosion welding and diffusion bonding. A comprehensive study and recent advances in the metallurgical challenges of welding dissimilar metals will be presented. Difficulties and future aspects of the dissimilar welding field will be also discussed.

Keywords: *Welding, Dissimilar Metals, Microstructures, Properties*

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**5th International Conference on Sustainable Science and Technology
(ICSuSaT-2022)**

01-03 July 2022, İstanbul-TURKIYE

Social Network Data Analytics

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ABSTRACT

Social life has been changing and also developing from day to day and thus using of social network becoming important. In this work Social Network Data Analytics will be detailed.

Keywords: *Social data, Network Data, Analytics*

Engineering Properties and Mineralogical Identification of Clay Soil from Trusmadi Formation in Bundu Tuhan, Saba

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ABSTRACT

The intensive weathering process of metasedimentary rock in Bundu Tuhan, Sabah, resulted in the formation of a thick soil profile and clay soil. This geological background in the area is mainly made up of the metasedimentary rock of the Trusmadi Formation, with an age of around Palaeocene to Middle Eocene. The parent rock was characterized by the interbedded of dark grey shale and thin sandstone. The study area is prone to soil creeping activity, especially in the thick soil of the Trusmadi Formation's slopes. Soil samples from three slopes were selected for further laboratory analysis and mineralogy study. The results of the analysis show that all soil samples are poorly sorted materials which are classified as sandy - silty clay soil and silty clay soil. The moisture content was 25.98%–37.10%, and the plasticity index ranged from 18.86%–23.91%. The soil classified as inactive to a normal type of clay with a very high swelling capacity. The maximum dry density ranged from 1.45 – 1.53 Mg/m³ and optimum moisture content of 25.00% - 25.40%. The result of the analysis shows all samples are classified as low permeability soil. As a summary, the creeping process of clay soil influenced by the mineralogical content which shows the appearance of kaolinite and illite of clay minerals as well as quartz minerals.

Keywords: Trusmadi Formation, clayey soil, mineralogy, soil creeping

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Sustainable Decision Making basing on Science and Technology

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ABSTRACT

Using some prediction approach becomes important on science and technology. Sustainable Decision making is one of them and it has many different application fields. In this work the importance of Sustainable Decision Making basing on Science and Technology will be detailed.

Keywords: *Sustainable Decision Making, ANN, Science and Technology*

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

O_73

Bacteriocin-like activity of some lactic acid bacteria isolated from artisanal hardaliye pickle

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we examined bacteriocin-like activity of 40 lactic acid bacteria (LAB) isolated from hardaliye pickle which is traditional food in Turkey, against to indicator pathogen bacteria. Initial LAB number (40) decreased to 20 according to diameters and stability of zones and were continued for study with these bacteria. Our purpose in this study was whether these isolates have an bacteriocin-like antibacterial activity. Agar-Sandwich method was chose as a method amongst antibacterial activity determination methods. Each test was achieved three times in accordance with this method and optimum agar initial pH and incubation temperature were determined. Otherwise effect of different proteolytic enzymes and catalase on bacteriocin-like antibacterial activity of these bacteria were determined. As a result pH 4,5 and 35°C were found as an available agar pH and incubation temperature, respectively. Some isolates were affected by proteolytic enzymes and the other some were not influenced by enzyme treatments. None of isolates lose activity completely by proteolytic enzyme treatment. Staphylococcus aureus was the most sensitive against bacteriocin-like antibacterial activity. This study may lead use of these bacteria have bacteriocin-like activity in food industry and in this way it will support food safety.

Keywords: *Antibacterial activity, bacteriocin, lactic acid bacteria*

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O_74

Radyoterapide kullanılan a-Si elektronik portal görüntüleme sisteminin in-vivo dozimetri için performans Değerlendirmesi

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ABSTRACT

YART çok yapraklı kolimatörlerle(ÇYK) şekillendirilmiş çoklu alan ve alt alanlardan radyoterapi uygulanması temeline dayanır. YART'ın çok basamaklı planlama ve uygulama yönteminde hastalara doğru dozun verildiğini kontrol eden kalite kontrol(KK) yöntemleri gerekmektedir. Lineer hızlandırıcıya(LINAK) entegre amorf silikon(a-Si) elektronik portal görüntüleme(EPG) sistemlerinin öncelikli amacı hastanın tedavi pozisyonunun kontrolü iken, YART planınınin tedavi öncesi dozimetrik KK'de kullanımı son zamanlarda rutin olarak uygulanmaktadır. Hasta tedavisi sırasında (in-vivo) EPG dozimetriyle YART KK'ü ise halen araştırılan bir konudur. Bu çalışmada kliniğimiz Varian CLINAC DHX LINAK'a entegre aSi1000 EPG sisteminin in-vivo dozimetri için kullanılabilirliğini test etmek amaçlanmıştır. 6MV - 100, 75, 40, 20, 10, 5 MU ile her bir ışınlama değerlerinde 17 ardışık ışınlama yapılarak tekrarlanabilirlik testi gerçekleştirildi. Katı su fantomunda 1mm-30cm arasında değişen kalınlıklarda ölçüm alınarak fantom kalınlığına karşı doz yanıtı incelendi ve iyon odası ölçümleri ile karşılaştırıldı. Tekrarlanabilirlik ölçümüne göre 100MU için ortalama değerler $0,689\pm 0,0008$ ve 10MU için $0,0639\pm 0,0008$ olarak hesaplanmıştır. Ölçümlerin ortalamadan yüzde farkı ise 100MU için ortalama $\%0,108\pm 0,0517$ ve 10MU için $\%1,095\pm 0,671$ hesaplanmıştır. Test sonuçlarımız göstermiştir ki, yüksek MU değerlerinde EPG dozimetrisinin tekrarlanabilirliği ve güvenilirliği oldukça iyi iken, düşük MU değerlerinde tekrarlı ölçümlerin kararlılığı daha azdır. EPG dozimetriyle YART in-vivo KK'ü hızlı, kolay, tekrarlanabilir ve hastaya ek doz verilmesine gerek olmayan bir yöntemdir.

Keywords: yoğunluk ayarlı radyoterapi, elektronik portal görüntüleme, in-vivo dozimetri, kalite kontrol

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O_2

Treatment of Dirac oscillator in Noncommutative geometry

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we study the relativistic oscillator Dirac under the influence of a uniform magnetic field in the non-commutation relations of non-commutative algebra. Where we have obtained the energy eigenvalues and the corresponding wave function using a direct method, to observe that the system has been influenced by the NC geometry.

Keywords: *non-commutative algebra, Dirac oscillator, magnetic field*

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O_3

Assessment of adverse effects of background noise on employees in a Call center

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ABSTRACT

Human productivity refers to the optimal use of human talent, knowledge, and skills in order to achieve maximum performance of the organization. The level of benefits for the company is determined by personal, organizational, social, and environmental factors such as noise, lighting, temperature, air quality, etc. In fact, noise exposure is not limited to the work environment and can be also experienced during leisure activities. There are numerous studies that examine the impact of noise on the physical health of respondents. In this paper, the ambient noise in the Call Center was examined, in which the main work activity is conversation and communication with customers. In order to investigate ambient noise, measurements of sound pressure levels in the workplace were performed. The level of ambient noise is a very important factor because it, directly and indirectly, affects work productivity and the atmosphere. Sound pressure measurements showed that the mean value of L_{eq} is 67.88 (2.48) dBA, which significantly exceeds the allowable value of 50 dBA. Frequency characteristics of equivalent values at 1/3 octave show a maximum at 630 Hz. A survey questionnaire is used to assess the negative effects of ambient noise on the working atmosphere, productivity, and certain psychophysical aspects of the individual and was conducted amongst 190 workers. Data analysis was performed in the SPSS program and showed that noise mostly influences the lack of concentration and focus on work. This statement is especially true for employees who have significant work experience in this company.

Keywords: *Background noise, Sound pressure levels, Questionnaire survey*

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O_4

Prediction of the natural rubber mechanical properties using machine learning

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ABSTRACT

Developing and investigating Machine Learning (ML) model to predict samples' mechanical properties of commercially available natural rubber with different type of the filler, was the aim of this study. During the rubber mixing, as a filler in the mixture were used traditional carbon black (CB) and biochar made by hydrothermal carbonization treatment of hardwood waste biomass. The samples were prepared following the same procedure and recipe, using different content of CB or biochar (0, 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 phr). Shore A durometer and dynamic extensometer were used to investigate the samples' hardness and tensile strength, respectively. The proposed model was developed in a Python framework, containing two hidden layers with 10 neurons, where the model and activation function were Sequential and Softplus, respectively. The training of the network was conducted for samples with 0, 10, 30 and 50 phr CB or biochar, and experimental data containing 20 and 40 phr were used for determining numerical error. The proposed ML model was used to predict the mechanical properties for samples containing 20 and 40 phr of the filler. Obtained solutions were confirmed as accurate prediction using numerical methods for tested content of the filler, where MAPE and MSE values were less than 4.07% and 0.72, respectively.

Keywords: *Natural rubber, Machine learning, Mechanical properties, Carbon black, Biochar*

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O_5

Assessment of adverse effects of background noise on employees in a Call center

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ABSTRACT

The Welding process is efficient and reliable as a means of joining metals. Some welds will be prepared by Metal Inert Gas (MIG) and Tungsten Inert Gas (TIG) techniques. Small scale trial welding experiments, in the light of field joint of plate have been planned to perform on 6 mm plate thicknesses of St37 low alloy and double V-groove joint is used. The input parameters for each experiment are welding current, voltage, gas flow, feeding speed and bevel angle, where the output parameters are hardness, elongation and maximum tensile strength. The experimental data optimized by grey relational analysis (GRA) technique, and then studied it by multi regression and reliability analysis in order to find the most reliable process. Using MANOVA analysis to find out percentage contribution of each input parameter for obtaining optimal conditions. A grey relational analysis (GRA) technique was used for optimization of different values. By analyzing the Grey relational grade (GRG), the optimum parameters was determined. Also by reliability analysis of GRG, indicating the most reliable process.

Keywords: MANOVA, GRA, Optimization, Reliability, MIG Welding, TIG Welding

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O_6

Anatomical pathways of nociception

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ABSTRACT

Pain is an unpleasant and emotional sensation that can be a warning sign or the revelation of an illness. It is a complex phenomenon with sensory, cognitive and affective components. There are four main processes of pain: transduction, transmission, modulation and perception.

We will look at the anatomy of the afferent pathways that conduct nociceptive impulses from the periphery to the higher nerve centres.

Description of the afferent pathways

1 - Nociceptors

The nociceptive nerve endings are small and scattered and can pick up mechanical (pressure, pinch), thermal and chemical pain stimuli.

2-The afferent pathways:

- They are made up of three neurons
- There are two major targets: the thalamus and the medial reticular formation of the brainstem.
- There are two major ascending pathways for pain:
- A direct lateral spinothalamic pathway.
- An indirect medial spinoreticulothalamic pathway.

Discussion/Conclusion

Most of what we know about the anatomy and physiology of pain comes from experimental studies of cutaneous pain, whereas most of it actually comes from deep tissue, musculoskeletal or visceral.

Lesions of the ventrocaudal thalamus and somatosensory cortex produce lasting deficits in the sensory aspects of pain.

Lesions of the medial thalamus have very little effect on the sensation of pain, but the emotional or reactive aspects may be completely suppressed (Barber, 1959).

Keywords: *Afferent pathways Anatomy Nociception*

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O_7

The Graphics Tablet And Its Contribution To Anatomy Teaching

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ABSTRACT

1- Introduction/Objectives

The teaching of anatomy in medical schools varies from one teacher to another, from drawings on a blackboard to Power Point slides.

Although video projection of courses has the advantage of great visibility and time saving, it is devoid of the desired interactivity between learners and teachers.

Drawing in real time has this pedagogical advantage, which a graphics tablet could enrich and perfect.

The objective of this presentation is to review the literature on the contribution of this tool to teaching in general and anatomy in particular.

2- Materials and methods

We selected three relevant studies that were carried out in medical schools. These are comparative studies between the teaching of anatomy by Power Point slides and the use of a graphic tablet to draw in real time with evaluation of the students' perception.

3- Results

- Study 1: Progression in the second test was greater in the "graphic tablet" group
- Study 2: In total, 99% of the students found the graphic tablet effective for learning anatomy.
- Study 3: Scores were significantly higher immediately in the cross-section (using the graphics tablet) compared to the sagittal section (using PowerPoint).

4- Conclusion

The contribution of the graphic tablet in the teaching of anatomy is proven, which nevertheless requires learning and training of teachers.

Keywords: teaching, anatomy, graphics tablet.

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O_8

Review Of The Literature On The Probable Causes Of Lateral Ankle Sprain

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ABSTRACT

Lateral ankle sprain is a very common and sometimes disabling condition. The causes of its occurrence and recurrence are still poorly understood, despite numerous studies.

Its prevention, and that of recurrences, should be a public health objective within a medico-economic framework.

The aim of this presentation is to review the probable causes of this pathology, as reported in the literature.

Etiologies

According to the studies carried out, the probable causes are divided into two parts: intrinsic factors (mechanical and neuromuscular), extrinsic factors and other discussed causes.

Discussion

According to the literature, many causes of inborn or acquired instability can lead to sprains. The mechanisms involved in a first episode of sprain do not seem to differ from the causes leading to chronic ankle instability.

Conclusion

The proposed factors of occurrence and recurrence of ankle sprains, particularly lateral sprains, remain controversial and require further investigation.

However, anatomical variations in the stabilising components of the ankle appear to be instability factors, predisposing to ankle sprains.

Keywords : sprain, ankles, causes

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The museum of the anatomy laboratory of Algiers

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ABSTRACT

The laboratory of anatomy of the faculty of medicine of Algiers is located at the university of Algiers Benyoucef Benkheda which is one of the oldest universities of the African continent. It was founded by decree on 4 August 1857.

A preparatory school of Medicine and Pharmacy was thus created, this school being attached to the Faculty of Medicine of Montpellier. The new school was officially opened on 15 January 1859. It had seven chairs, including a chair of anatomy and physiology. In 1889, the Preparatory School of Algiers was transformed into a full-fledged School of Medicine and Pharmacy, and in 1909, a University was established in Algiers, and the School was transformed into a mixed Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy. A decree of 4 January 1910 established sixteen chairs, including one for anatomy.

The anatomy laboratory houses the museum with very rare anatomical models, exceptional pieces such as the skin parchment, the giant skull base, and antique equipment such as stereoscopes.

Because of the richness of its heritage, the laboratory of anatomy of Algiers and particularly its museum, is a place of visit not only for the students, but also for foreign and official delegations.

The museum of the anatomy laboratory is considered as national heritage.

Keywords: Laboratory, museum, anatomy

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O_10

**Angiotensin Converting Enzyme (ACE) Gene
Insertion/Deletion Polymorphism and susceptibility to
schizophrenia: A case-control study**

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ABSTRACT

The ACE enzyme activity in different brain regions of schizophrenia patients is increased, suggesting a possible involvement of this enzyme in psychiatric disorders. More recently, literature data have focused on the ACE insertion (I)/ deletion(D) polymorphism in schizophrenia and the results obtained were very heterogeneous. The objective of our study was to evaluate the relationship between this polymorphism and the risk of schizophrenia.

Our study included 114 controls divided into 67 (58.77) men and 47 (41.23%) women, with a sex ratio of 1.42. And 42 schizophrenia patients of which 36 (84.44) are male and 6 female with a sex ratio of 6 and a p-value <001. The search for the ACE I/D polymorphism gene was performed by simple PCR/RFLP.

In patients, the genotypic frequencies of the ACE I/D polymorphism were as follows: 13.33% are heterozygous I/D, 66.66% are D/D homozygous, and 13.33% are I/I homozygous. In controls, we therefore noted that the dominant genotype is the heterozygous genotype I/D with a rate of 51.75%, while the homozygous genotype I/D is the least common with a 5.26% rate and a frequency of 40.35% for genotype I/I. Our results did not reveal any association between ACE I/D polymorphism and susceptibility to schizophrenia since Odds ratios I/I vs D/D is nonsignificant 1.97 (0.50-7.69) with p = 0.21 not significant. On the other hand, the odds ratio I/I + I/D vs D/D is close to the significance 0.45 (0.20-1.04) with a p = 0.06. Our results are consistent with many data from the literature.

Keywords: ACE, ACE gene I/D polymorphism, Schizophrenia

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O_11

Catalytic activity of Co/HMS in the conversion of p-nitrophenol to p-aminophenol

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ABSTRACT

P-aminophenol (PAP) is an important pharmaceutical intermediate for the manufacture of paracetamol. Conventionally, PAP is manufactured by iron-acid reduction of p-nitrochlorobenzene or p-nitrophenol, which are multistep processes. A single-step catalytic hydrogenation of nitrobenzene to PAP by supported noble metal catalysts in aqueous acid medium was reported to be more environmentally acceptable and more efficient because of the simple workup of reaction crude. However the selectivity of PAP is very low. With the growing demand for PAP, direct catalytic hydrogenation of p-nitrophenol to PAP becomes important. In our knowledge, up to now, no work has been reported on the liquid phase p-nitrophenol hydrogenation over mesoporous HMS molecular sieves supported metal catalysts. Therefore, this work attempted to perform the catalytic hydrogenation of p-nitrophenol to PAP over Co/HMS catalyst. During the process of catalytic hydrogenation, higher PAP selectivity was obtained.

Keywords: PAP, HMS, Reduction

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Prostate cancer : the psa marker will soon be replaced!

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ABSTRACT

Prostate cancer is a major cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, it is the second leading cause of cancer death in men.

The discovery and then the use of the serum PSA assay have considerably changed the modalities of diagnosis of prostate cancer over more than 20 years. But its use is increasingly controversial. The limitations of PSA have made the development of new biomarkers a necessity, which could soon be used to better detect this cancer.

Our study aims to take stock of the biological markers that have now led to diagnostic tests, whether marketed or not.

The phi index concept integrates serum assays of total PSA, free PSA, and pro-PSA into a more efficient algorithm.

When related to urinary PSA, several biomarkers have already outperformed certain aspects of serum PSA performance. Currently, the urinary assay of PCA3 has proven its clinical relevance in the prediction of positivity of reforested prostates. Recently AMACR has been reported as an excellent marker as well as MMP.

The discovery of prostate cancer fusion genes holds promise both as a marker and as a potential therapeutic target.

Despite the PSA test's lack of sensitivity and specificity, it remains the first-line test in prostate cancer screening; Careful validation of emerging biomarkers can help address hitherto unresolved clinical challenges and guide clinicians toward better diagnostics and treatment options for prostate cancer. With the arsenal of new alternative biomarkers, prostate cancer is about to enter an era of personalized medicine

Keywords: *Prostate cancer, PSA, new biomarkers, the urinary assay of PCA3, prostate cancer fusion genes*

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O_13

Highlighting Salmon's artery (fixing artery of the arch of the inferior thyroid artery) about a case.

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ABSTRACT

Objective: search for possible variations in the branches of the inferior thyroid artery

Materials: Our study material is represented by anatomical subjects.

The dissection was performed at the Normal Anatomy Laboratory of the Clermont-Ferrand Organ Donation Center in France

Method: We realized a vascular injection colored with latex from the subclavian with a 5cc syringe

Results: we were able to identify the collateral and terminal branches of the inferior thyroid artery and more particularly a prevertebral muscular branch detaching from the first arch of the inferior thyroid artery intended for the longus muscle of the neck which would be at the origin of the first arch made by the inferior thyroid artery.

Discussion: according to the literature review, only one case was reported by PATURET.G after that of SALMON, This fixing artery of the arch of the inferior thyroid artery of Salmon clinging to the sheath of the longus muscle of the neck and becomes fixing artery of the arch of the inferior thyroid artery (5%).

Could this artery be the cause of the variations in the path of the inferior thyroid artery? However to confirm these data; further study is desirable.

Keywords: Arteries of the thyroid gland¹; Inferior thyroid artery², Thyroidectomy³

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O_14

The fine caliber of the inferior laryngeal nerve can be a source of iatrogenic lesion

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ABSTRACT

Objective: to search for conditional variations in caliber of the inferior laryngeal nerve at the level of the inferior poles of the thyroid gland.

Materials: 107 patients, including 97 women and 10 men, referred to the Oto-Rhino-Laryngology Department of the Constantine University Hospital for a malignant thyroid disease, all benefited from a total thyroidectomy

Methods and results: This was a descriptive, cross-sectional prospective study. We proceeded to a dissection of the vasculo-nervous pedicle, the identification of the inferior laryngeal nerves allowed us to find, based on the surgeon's experience, possible macroscopic variations in the caliber of the inferior laryngeal nerve which can be a source of injury iatrogenic. On 20 nerves; 13 fine nerves (12.15%) of the cases on the right and 10 nerves (9.34%) of the cases on the left.

Discussion: our research in the literature, found only Page C which carried out a study by finding this variation in 12.68% on the right and 9.08% on the left.

The existence of these small nerves in our patients is at the origin of the difficulties of identification for the surgeon thus promoting the risk of iatrogenic lesion of the inferior laryngeal nerve.

Keywords: *nerves of the thyroid gland, inferior laryngeal nerve, thyroidectomy*

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The arch of the great saphenous vein (GSV) and its practical value in varicose vein surgery

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ABSTRACT

Targets :

- 1- Anatomical study Modal type of the arch of the great saphenous vein.
- 2- Study of the anatomical variations of the arch of the great saphenous vein and its venous confluences.

Summary:

The anatomy of the superficial veins of the lower limbs differ enormously from one individual to another, to the point that vein therapists, surgeons and Phlebologists generally precede a treatment of varicose veins with a superficial vein mapping.

True venous crossroads, the arch of the great saphenous vein receives a set of branches that should be known in their normal anatomy and in their variations because, essential rule during stripping, they must all be controlled. The arch of the great saphenous vein presents a great anatomical variation as well as the anatomical distribution of its tributaries, the lack of knowledge of which represents a non-negligible cause of recurrence after treatment of varicose veins.

Crossectomy is one of the essential gestures of varicose vein surgery and therefore its success depends on a good knowledge of the modal anatomy and the variations of the arch of the great saphenous vein.

Keywords: *cross of the great saphenous vein, anatomical variations of tributaries and crossectomy.*

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Acupuncture, between myth and reality. A review of the literature

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ABSTRACT

Acupuncture is one of the oldest medical practices in the world. It is part of traditional Chinese medicine, and its origins date back to the Neolithic period, estimated to be around 6000 years ago.

Long considered a cosmological science, imaginary, obscure and sometimes even a deception, acupuncture is in reality a real science based on proven anatomical and physiological foundations.

Our knowledge of traditional Chinese medicine, in particular acupuncture and meridian pathology, comes largely from a classic book, written some 2000 years ago; the Huangdi Neijing or Nei Jing or the "Yellow Emperor's Inner Classics", in which notions of dissections (vivisections) are quoted.

Modern research has demonstrated the existence of neuro-vascular nodes at the level of the acupuncture points, and experimental studies, most often carried out on animals, have highlighted certain neurophysiological bases to explain the analgesic effect of acupuncture in experimental situations.

The research on acupuncture shows that it is a scientifically based medical practice and that it has been damaged by the mistranslation of Chinese texts into other languages.

Keywords: *acupuncture, science, anatomy, physiology*

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Macroscopic and morphometric study of the Berrettini anastomosis

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ABSTRACT

Two anastomoses at the level of the palm of the hand between the median and the ulnar nerve are known: one deep, and the second superficial and sensitive, called Berrettini.

The objective of this study is to evaluate the prevalence of Berrettini and to specify the topography and morphology with respect to the retinaculum of the flexors.

Keywords: *ulnar nerve - median nerve - anastomotic branch - prevalence of anastomosis - morphometric study.*

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Anatomo-clinical study of the ulnar canal at the wrist

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ABSTRACT

The ulnar canal is an osteo-fibrous space located on the lateral face of the pisiform. It originates at the proximal edge of the palmar carpal ligament to the fibrous arch of the hypothenarians. At this level the nerve can be the seat of a compression. (1) (2) (3)

The aim of our work is to

- An in-depth anatomical study of the canal, through a series of wrist and hand dissections
- A morphometric study of the canal and its anatomical elements.

Keywords: *ulnar canal - ulnar nerve - compression - canal syndrome - morphometry*

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Macroscopic and morphometric study of the hypothenar muscle arch

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ABSTRACT

A fibrous arch is described between the pisiform bone and the hamulus (arch of Uriburu, arch of the hypothenar muscles [1]. It represents a preferential site for compression of the deep branch of the ulnar nerve (Uriburu et al 1976). The purpose of this work is to show the structure of the arch of the hypothenar muscles. [2].

Keywords: *macroscopic study, the hypothenar arch, structure.*

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Compression of the deep terminal branch of the ulnar nerve: a case report.

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ABSTRACT

At the level of the wrist, the ulnar nerve is placed inside the ulnar vessels and is divided into its terminal branches: one superficial sensory and the other deep motor. [1] Along its course, the deep branch innervates the muscles of the hypothenar eminence, the interosseous and lumbrical muscles of the 3rd and 4th spaces, the adductor muscle of the thumb, the deep bundle of the flexor digitorum brevis and the first dorsal interosseus.

- The goal is to show that the deep branch is exclusively motor and its impairment results in paralysis of the last two fingers of the hand, associated with a positive ulnar claw sign. [2]

Keywords: *macroscopic study of the deep terminal branch of the ulnar nerve, compression, ulnar claw sign.*

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The C677T of the MTHFR gene and the risk of schizophrenia in a population of Eastern Algeria

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INTRODUCTION

Schizophrenia is a complex psychotic disorder that affects about 1% of the general population worldwide. Interactions between environmental factors and genetic vulnerability have been suggested as etiological factors of this disease. Several studies have shown that the 677T allele of the MTHFR gene is associated with high homocysteine levels and low plasma folate and vitamin B12 levels.

We wanted to investigate a possible relationship between the C677T polymorphism of the MTHFR gene and the plasma homocysteine level in schizophrenic patients from Eastern Algeria

Patients and methods

Our study included 114 controls and 42 schizophrenics. The C677T mutation of the MTHFR gene was detected by PCR /RFLP using the restriction enzyme Hinf I.

Results

A significant association between male sex (82.14%), smoking (69.77% vs 46.55%), cannabis use (39.95% vs 00%), family morbidity (56.86% vs 7.41%) and plasma folate levels was shown. However, Vitamin B12 and homocysteine levels showed no association with schizophrenia.

We also found a strong association between the homozygous TT mutated genotype of the MTHFR gene and schizophrenia with odds ratios of TT vs CC=30.87 CI (7.21-153.23)p<0.00001 and TT+CT vs CC=9.16IC(3.47-24.78) p<0.00001.

Conclusion

Our results showed that the TT genotype of the MTHFR gene was a risk factor for the development of the schizophrenia.

Keywords: MTHFR C677T polymorphism, schizophrenia, homocysteine, folate, vitamin B12.

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O_22

Acute pancreatitis and diabetes mellitus : A cause and effect loop

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Incidence of acute pancreatitis(AP) is clearly increasing; AP cause diabetes mellitus (DM) as well as complicate DM. AP's incidence in diabetics is 4.75 cases/1000/year versus 1.65 in the non-diabetic population.

Objective: Study the risk factors for the occurrence of AP in diabetics.

Patients & Methods: Five cases of AP occurring in diabetic patients during their hospitalization in the Diabetology department. AP is diagnosed in front of 2 criteria among the following 3: Clinical symptoms, Lipasemia > 3 times the normal and Abnormal pancreatic imaging. Etiological investigation of AP was based on clinical data, metabolic work-up, viral hepatitis serology, abdominal ultrasound, abdominal CT±MRI. AP's severity was assessed according to the Atlanta 2012 classification.

Result: Patients(3 women/2 men) aged 39±18 years, mean HbA1c 11%, mean BMI 26 kg/m². AP was 3 times moderately severe and 2 times simple, established at less than 7 days of hospitalization. The causes of AP was:

- Micro-multi-lithiasis bladder during pregnancy,
- Cholecystitis and Corticotherapy in a Type2 DM,
- Hypertriglyceridemia(17g/l) and diabetic ketosis in DM secondary to Hypercorticism,
- Diabetic ketoacidosis in a Type1 DM
- Pancreatic cyst and high-dose corticosteroid in a Type2 DM who had a second attack in less than 12 days

Discussion: The relationship between exocrine pancreas and diabetes is complex. DM poorly controlled, increases the risk of AP because of associated comorbidities (obesity, dyslipidemia, polypharmacy), and the risk of gallstones. AP-Hypertriglyceridemia-Acidoketosis triangle is of complex pathophysiology still poorly elucidated, with a cause and effect loop. The triglyceride pathway is often incriminated, which can be associated with ketoacidosis. Persistent digestive symptoms despite regression of ketosis should raise suspicion of AP. The role of corticosteroid therapy in AP is still controversial.

Keywords: Acute pancreatitis Diabetes Mellitus Ketoacidosis Hypertriglyceridemia

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Predictive Maintenance of Rotating Machines Industrial application and proposal of technological solutions

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ABSTRACT

The study and analysis of the dynamic behavior of mechanical systems are of great interest in the industrial field. They allow, among other things, to reduce the vibratory levels and the harmful consequences that they can engender.

The design of machines capable of performing well under the operating conditions is necessary to avoid the problems of instabilities, a source of catastrophic failure or the main cause is the unbalance generated by the rotational movement.

In this work, we propose to study the dynamic behavior of an industrial machine: the cellulose crusher. It has several mechanical faults: unbalance fault, bearing faults, wear faults, etc.

The goal is to follow up on faults to make the necessary corrections and remedy these problems.

A modeling, a theoretical study and a numerical simulation of the rotor carrying the crusher are carried out.

Vibration measurements are taken using appropriate instrumentation.

The results of the numerical simulation, the theoretical study and the experiment are compared with each other. We determine the severity of mechanical faults and their consequences on the dynamic behavior of the machine.

The solutions proposed are technological

Keywords: *Vibration analysis, Unbalance, Bearing*

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Influence of faults on the dynamic behavior of a rotating system. Application to an industrial machine and proposal of technological solutions

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ABSTRACT

In this work, we propose to study the dynamic behavior of an industrial machine: the cellulose shredder. It has several mechanical faults:

- unbalance fault on the rotor generating high-level vibrations.
- bearing defects, wear defects, etc.

The objective is to follow up on faults to make the necessary corrections and remedy these problems.

A modeling, a theoretical study and a numerical simulation of the rotor carrying the crusher are carried out.

Also, we study the vibratory behavior of the entire kinematic chain of the machine. We take samples of vibratory measurements using appropriate instrumentation.

The results of the numerical simulation, the theoretical study and the experiment are compared with each other. We determine the severity of mechanical faults and their consequences on the dynamic behavior of the machine.

The solutions proposed are technological.

Keywords: *Shredder, imbalance, wear.*

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Capacity Analysis for Urban Area Scenario for Long Term Evolution–Advanced with Wireless Network Service

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ABSTRACT

In order to meet the increasing demand and stringent design requirements for coverage expansion and capacity enhancement. Relay Node (RN) has been considered as a promising solution, in urban area scenario.

However; the user density is quite high and often non-uniformly distributed. The main objective of the RN is to enhance the capacity.

This innovation increases the cell-edge coverage radius and through put as well as enhances the usage efficiency of network resources. In fact, the basic idea of relay is to forward signals through one or more relay nodes (RNs) before retransmitting to the destination node [3].

In this paper, we propose how RN can be made compact to allow more flexible deployment. We can apply for Wireless Network Service.

Keywords: *Wireless network, LTE-A, Capacity Analysis, Urban Area.*

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Composite Joint Damage Analysis By Digital Image Correlation

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ABSTRACT

In the present work, an experimental study is carried out using digital image correlation (DIC) technique to analyze the damage and behavior of woven composite carbon / epoxy under tensile loading. The tension mechanisms associated with failure modes of bolted joints in advanced composites is studied, as well as displacement distribution and strain distribution. The evolution value of bolt angle inclination during tensile tests was studied. In order to compare the distribution of displacements and strains along the surface, figures of image mapping are made. Several factors that are responsible for the failure of fiber reinforced polymer composite materials are observed. It was found that strain concentrations observed in the specimens can be used to identify full-field damage onset and to monitor damage progression during loading. Moreover, there is interaction between laminate pattern, laminate thickness, fastener size and type, surface strain concentrations and out-of-plane displacement. Conclusions include a failure analysis associated with bolt angle inclinations and supported by microscopic visualizations of the composite specimen. The DIC results can be used to develop and accurately validate numerical models.

Keywords: Carbone, woven, damage, digital image, bolted joint; inclination of angle.

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Investigation Of The Electromagnetic Shielding Properties Of Fabrics Coated With Polymers

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ABSTRACT

The requirements of modern living conditions, the rapid development of technology, and the increase in the level of welfare increase the use of electrical and electronic devices. Many electrical-electronic devices used in homes emit radiation. Harmful radiation emitted by these electronic devices can adversely affect human health. In order to reduce this negative effect, shielding is applied and it is aimed at preventing electromagnetic scattering from entering the living body. Considering the anti-radiation standard developed by ICRP, many limit values have been determined in the world and in our country to limit them, and the term electromagnetic shielding and shielding materials have been developed. In this study, products such as doped polymer, ammonium persulfate, sulfuric acid, and boron were used as shielding aids. These chemical products were produced by coating the samples on two different fabrics (cotton-copper-silver, and polyester-copper-silver). Within the aforementioned method, using auxiliary chemical products, the fabric was sprayed with boron with an electromagnetic shielding feature and isocyanate material. The coating process was carried out in a laboratory-type coating machine. In accordance with various characterization analyzes, the differences between the electromagnetic shielding properties of the coated fabrics were investigated. It has been observed that materials such as polymer, ammonium persulfate, sulfuric acid, and boron used in the direction of the findings obtained in the study absorb the electromagnetic wave to a large extent and emit radiation more. In this way, it has been evaluated as having a high potential for use, since it will minimize the negative effects on living things by being used in workplaces, home environments, and baby and hospital rooms.

Keywords: Polymer, Electromagnetic shielding, Boron

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Constructing Socio-Religious Harmony Framework in Sabah, Malaysia Using Fuzzy Delphi Method Analysis

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to construct a framework of socio-religious harmony in Sabah which is unique in its own diverse culture and religions. This study employs the Fuzzy Delphi Method (FDM), prioritizing expert consensus in determining the investigation results. The study has selected seventeen experts from various professional backgrounds: academicians, policymakers, community leaders, non-government (NGO), and religious leaders. The results have identified four elements, and 20 of the 31 expert-agreed-upon criteria, which were then displayed hierarchically as a model of socio-religious harmony framework in Sabah. The finding also reveals the top ten highest ranking criteria agreed upon by experts for considering variables of establishing socio-religious harmony in Sabah. Ultimately, the study gives a clear framework for future studies to measure a level of social harmony in Sabah, and significantly contribute as a guideline throughout Malaysia as a whole.

Keywords: *religious tolerance, Sabah (East Malaysia); Fuzzy Delphi Method (FDM); Framework of socio-religious harmony*

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O_30

Influencing Factors for Environmental Sustainability Practices of SMEs: A Systematic Review

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ABSTRACT

In the recent era, the challenge of implementing environmental regulations is quite stringent for small and medium entrepreneurs due to global warming, waste management issue, and a dearth of natural resources. High consumption of energy, increase in carbon emissions, and consumers' concern for the safety and quality of products from SMEs are the barriers to the environmental sustainability of our globe. The study has analyzed the literature systematically over the last 7 years, from 2015 to 2022, to identify the key factors that have influenced the environmental sustainability practices of SMEs. 28 articles from Scopus, Google Scholar, and Web of Science database were identified by applying “factors” AND “environmental sustainability” AND “SMEs” keywords and inclusion as well as exclusion criteria. The study has uncovered recurring themes, including innovation, human capital, resources, strategy, capability, and stakeholders. Moreover, government laws and regulations, recycling, waste reduction, environment-friendly goods, minimization of pollution, and firm-level environmental management policy have also been identified as potential factors. The study would fill the literature gap based on a systematic analysis of environmental sustainability and SMEs and develop recommendations to accommodate the research gaps. Finally, this review would assist SMEs in prioritizing the leading factors and drivers that influence the implementation of sustainability practices.

Keywords: *Environmental, Sustainability, SMEs*

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O_31

A comparative study of serum creatinine dosage on two different automats: Dimension® EXL™ 200 and Architect ci 8200

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ABSTRACT

Creatinine is an essential biochemical parameter in clinical practice for the diagnosis of renal failure and for estimating the glomerular filtration rate (GFR) taken into account in therapeutic management. Today, various automated assay systems are available on the market. The reliability and quality of the results as well as the possibility of transferability between different systems are questioned.

Thus, the objective of this study carried out in the Biochemistry laboratory of the University Hospital of Constantine, during the period spread from January 30 to February 28, 2022, was to evaluate the correlation and concordance between the results of creatinine assays obtained by two different automats: Dimension® EXL™ 200 and Architect ci 8200 both based on the Jaffé kinetic method with elimination of bilirubin interference through its oxidation by potassium ferricyanide (Dimension® EXL™ 200).

A total of 58 samples covering the measurement range were tested and for each sample, the assays were performed in parallel on the two automats.

We found a good correlation between the two systems with a correlation coefficient $R = 0.998$ and a P value = 1.26×10^{-68} (< 0.05). The evaluation of the concordance by the realization of the graph according to Bland and Altman revealed a bias of 0.74 with a narrow interval of concordance, extending from (-1.81) to (+3.30) which affirms a perfect concordance between the results obtained by the two automats.

Thus, the two automats are interchangeable allowing a follow-up of patients by one or the other of the two systems.

Keywords: Creatinine, Architect ci 8200 automated system, Dimension® EXL™ 200 automated system, Correlation, Concordance, Transferability

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Liquidity Management Practices of Private Commercial Banks in Bangladesh for Sustainable Development

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ABSTRACT

Liquidity management is considered one of the critical issues in the banking sector for its sustainable development around the globe. Therefore, the current study intends to evaluate the liquidity management practice of the banking sector in Bangladesh from a sustainability perspective. The study is based on secondary data compiled from six sample banks' annual reports for the past five years. The study has found that the net working capital ratio and the deposit to assets ratio have a significant impact on the return on investment. However, the current ratio, cash ratio, loan deposit ratio, cash deposit ratio, and capital adequacy ratio have an insignificant impact on the return on investment of the sample banks over the study period. Furthermore, the results reveal that the different indicators of liquidity management have reported an insignificant impact on the return on capital employed ratio of the sample banks over the study period. The study also identifies that proper liquidity management practices drive the banking sector in Bangladesh towards sustainable development. In addition, the correlation coefficients indicate a positive correlation between cash deposit ratio and net working capital ratio but a negative correlation between deposit to assets ratio and capital adequacy ratio, loan to deposit ratio and cash ratio, and net working capital ratio and cash ratio.

Keywords: Liquidity, Commercial Banks, Sustainable Development, Bangladesh

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O_33

The removal of azo dye on ZnO/clay heterosystem by photocatalysis

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ABSTRACT

The current study aims to remove the textile dye basic red (RB46) by combining the adsorption and photocatalysis processes in the presence of a ZnO/clay heterosystem. The study consists of first preparing a clay impregnated with an elaborated ZnO semiconductor, which is then analysed using two Physico-chemical analytical techniques: X-ray diffraction and zero charge point. Second, the effect of operating factors on photocatalytic degradation was discussed, including the pH of the solution and the initial concentration.

The results demonstrated that linking the two processes of adsorption and photocatalysis revealed a synergistic effect between them. For an initial concentration of 20 mg/L, a pH of 7, a temperature of 25 °C, and a catalyst dose of 1 g/L, a photodegradation rate of 97.7% was reported. In general, these processes may be classified as clean-pollution processes that use renewable energy and are part of a long-term development strategy.

Keywords: RB46, Adsorption, Photocatalysis, ZnO, clay

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Azo-dyes photocatalytic degradation in aqueous suspension of ZnO under solar irradiation

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the photocatalytic degradation of food dye E110 employing a heterogeneous photocatalytic process under solar irradiation using ZnO. In the first part, the semiconductor ZnO was synthesised, characterised and analysed by different techniques: X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). The second part investigated the photodegradation of the azo dye under different operating parameters such as pH of the solution, catalyst dose, and initial concentration of dye. The optimum catalyst dose was found to be 0.5 g/L. A maximum rate of degradation was observed at pH=6.4.

The kinetic study of photocatalytic degradation of pollutants showed a very good yield, exceeding 88%. Depending on the dye concentration, the photocatalytic degradation follows pseudo-first-order kinetics. The trapping effects of different data demonstrated that the oxidation of E110 mainly occurred by the direct oxidation of h⁺ and •O₂⁻ radicals, with the •OH radicals playing only a small part in the direct oxidation process.

Keywords: Photocatalysis, solar irradiation, dyes E110, semiconductors, ZnO

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Design and Performance Analysis of a Smart Greenhouse Powered by a Controlled Solar Energy System

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ABSTRACT

This paper considers the solar power control of greenhouse which has been got a great concern of many researchers. A small greenhouse solar system was constructed in the direction of East-West in Baghdad (33.3 ° N, 34.4 ° E). The proposed system contains solar panels and counter movement with a single pass. The solar thermal system was monitored on the roof of a greenhouse. Smartening and solar power deriving of greenhouse were touched and worked toward its improvement. The solar panel combined with the greenhouse was cooled and tracked using a controlled air/water cooling system, in order to get higher efficiency and higher power as well. The climate inside the greenhouse was monitored to keep the temperature within the desired range required by the plant. The results showed that the greenhouse temperature was cooled to 26 °C and the solar panel temperature was cooled to around 35 °C. The greenhouse was then chilled and heated, the temperature of the soil was 27°C.

Keywords: Greenhouse SWH Solar Energy Thermal Performance Tracking System.

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Early Detection For Insecticides Biomonitoring On Vegetables Via Acetylcholinesterase From The Brain Tissue Of *Diodon Hystrix*

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ABSTRACT

The exploitation of acetylcholinesterase (AChE) as a biosensor tool for the detection of pesticide contamination was well documented and considered a sensitive method with low-cost operations, rapid detection, and easy to handle. In this study, the brain tissue of *Diodon hystrix* was extracted, followed by precipitation and affinity purification using ammonium sulfate and procainamide Sepharose 6B, respectively. The enzyme was electrophoresed using Native-PAGE showed that the molecular weight was assessed to be ~ 135 kDa. Next, *D. hystrix* AChE was exposed to 2 mg.L⁻¹ of organophosphate. The result shows all the OP capable to inhibit more than 50% of AChE activity and ordered in ascending percentage of inhibition; chlorpyrifos = dimethoate < diazinon < trichlorfon ≤ acephate < malathion < parathion. However, the sensitivity is based on half-maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀), malathion shows the highest followed by dimethoate and chlorpyrifos at 0.036, 0.092, and 0.098 mg.L⁻¹. *Spinacia oleracea* was separately treated with different commercial/formulated OP. On the first day of the treatment of malathion, dimethoate, and chlorpyrifos, the activity of AChE was inhibited by more than 80% except for diazinon which the enzyme activity was significantly inhibited after seven days of treatment. However, at the end of the treatment, on day 14th, AChE activity was not affected considering the toxicity of OPs disappeared due to a decrease in their persistence and resistance. This study proves the capability of AChE from the brain tissue of *Diodon hystrix* as an alternative source for the development of biosensor tools to be used as a preliminary screening on food contaminants, especially pesticides.

Keywords: *acetylcholinesterase, Diodon hystrix, organophosphate, IC₅₀.*

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Preparation and Long-Term Stabilization of Electrospun Polysaccharide Nanofiber Membranes as a Potential for Biomaterials

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ABSTRACT

Electrospinning technique is extensively used to produce interconnected three-dimensional nonwoven nanofibers with high specific surface to volume ratio. Unique continuous nano-scale structure, high porosity and improved mechanical performances make them attractive for applications in the area of biomedical engineering, active packaging and separation processes. Pullulan is an extracellular and microbial polysaccharide generated by the activity of fungus *Aerobasidium pullulans*. Owing to its linear structure comprised of α -(1 \rightarrow 6)-linked maltotriose units, it is regarded as edible, biocompatible and material obtained from renewable resources. Owing to their cytocompatibility, electrospun pullulan is an excellent candidate for mimicking the native extracellular matrix. Thanks to its solubility in water, pullulan nanofibers can be easily produced from water solutions, highlighting the green approach of their manufacturing. However, the resulting nanomats are therefore instable under hydrated conditions resulting in poor mechanical properties, losing their unique nanofibrous structure and limiting its practical applications. According to the mentioned above, pullulan nanofiber membranes were prepared from water systems via electrospinning technique and further stabilized by in-situ chemical crosslinking using trisodium trimetaphosphate (SMP) (5 and 10 wt.% per polymer weight) under alkaline conditions. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) were performed to evaluate structure and thermal stability as well as to determine the morphology and diameter of the obtained nanostructures. In addition, water solubility of the cross-linked pullulan nanofiber membranes were presented and compared to the untreated samples. Taken together, the result show significant improvement in water resistance and superiority of polysaccharide nanomaterials.

Keywords: *Electrospinning Nanomaterials Biomaterials*

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⁴⁰K natural radioactivity for sand samples

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ABSTRACT

All living things in the world have been living under the influence of natural radioactivity caused by long half-life radioactive elements since the existence of the universe. Determining the concentration of these radioactive elements, which vary according to the geographical and geological structure of each region, is especially important for public health. One of the most important of these radioactive elements is Potassium-40 (⁴⁰K). In this study, Potassium-40 activity concentration of sand samples collected from Alacalı beach in İstanbul-Şişli district was measured by using NaI (TI) detector gamma spectroscopy system. The activity concentrations obtained are compared with the determined world averages.

Keywords: Potassium-40 activity concentration, Alacalı beach, Gamma spectroscopy, İstanbul-Şişli

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Swelling properties of polyurethane hydrogels

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ABSTRACT

Because of their similarity to soft tissues, hydrogels are ideal for use in regenerative medicine. However, polymers that are known for their compact structure, great properties and ability to imitate soft tissues are polyurethanes. Polyurethanes (PU), known as hydrophilic or insoluble in water, can be modified by incorporating hydrophilic soft segments, e.g. poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO), in order to increase their hydrophilicity. In this paper, new PU hydrogels were prepared by the polymerization of aliphatic diisocyanate and high molecular weight diol. The goal was to obtain hydrogel with a uniform structure, which is not porous. Synthesis was done in two different environments, in room conditions at elevated temperature (60 °C) and in vacuum at 25 °C. In synthesis, 2.7 functional isocyanates, poly(ethylene oxide) of molecular weight 2000, 6000 and 10000 g/mol, with the appropriate initiator, were polymerized in tetrahydrofuran as a solvent, stirring on magnetic stirrer. The stirring was carried out at low speeds to avoid the formation of air bubbles. After the synthesis, the samples were dried and then subjected to characterization on infrared spectroscopy and swelling. The FTIR results show that the formation of the NCO group was completed and a quantity reaction was achieved. Swelling ratio of polyurethane hydrogels were 150%/215% (with PEG 2000), 360%/495% (with PEG6000) and 850%/720% (with PEG 10000), depending of the synthesis temperature.

Keywords: Polyurethane, Swelling ratio, Infrared spectroscopy

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First evidence of microplastics in Moon jelly (*Aurelia aurita*, Linnaeus, 1758); a preliminary study from Gökova Bay (Southern Turkey)

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ABSTRACT

Microplastics (MPs) pollution is a concern in many nearshore ecosystems, and it is critical to understand how MP's affect nearshore marine biota. This study reports the occurrence of MP's in specimens of the jellyfish Moon jelly (*Aurelia aurita*, Linnaeus, 1758) sampled from Gökova Bay, Southern Turkey. To this aim, in 2020 12 specimens of Moon jelly were sampled in the inner gulf region of the bay and brought to the laboratory. After being measured (bell diameters in cm and weights in gr) specimens were stored under suitable conditions until analysis. Samples were processed with H₂O₂ (60%) to remove the organic material and the remaining liquid part was filtered through glass fiber filters (GF/F). Dried filters were observed under a stereo microscope for MP's count, and then further examined using the micro-Raman technique. Thus, MP's were specified both qualitatively and quantitatively. A mean of 13.08 ± 2.81 microplastics was detected in each sample. The most dominant MP's in terms of color were black and red (63.69% and 35.03%, respectively), while the most dominant group in terms of shape was fibril-shaped (88.53%) MP's. A strong positive correlation was determined between the bell diameter and body weight of Moon jelly with the amount of MP's ($r= 0.927$, $r= 0.821$, respectively). The result represents the first report of MP's occurrence in jellyfish from Turkish waters and suggest that Molly jelly, and jellyfish in general, can be used as bioindicators of MP's pollution.

Keywords: *Microplastics, Jellyfish, micro-raman*

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Image Classification using CNN

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an observational investigation of the result of normal convolutionary brain organizations (CNNs) progressively video feeds to perceive objects. Alex Nets, GoogLeNet, and ResNet50 are the most well-known brain convolutional networks for object discovery and item class order from pictures. There are a scope of picture informational indexes accessible for actually taking a look at the exhibition of different sorts of CNNs. An ImageNet dataset, CIFAR10, CIFAR100, and MNIST picture informational collections are the generally distinguished benchmark datasets for evaluating the exhibition of a convolutionary brain organization. The point of this exploration is to analyze the proficiency of three normal organizations: Alex Net, GoogLeNet, and ResNet50. For our investigation, we took three most normal informational collections, ImageNet, CIFAR10, and CIFAR100, as testing the presentation of an organization on a solitary informational collection doesn't uncover its actual abilities and restrictions. It ought to be recollected that recordings are not utilized as a dataset for readiness, but rather as a dataset for research. That's what our audit uncovers, comparative with Alex Net, GoogLeNet and ResNet50 can recognize objects with more prominent precision. What's more, the presentation of qualified CNNs contrasts incredibly across different article classes and consequently, we will address the expected clarifications for this

Keywords: *Deep Learning, CNN, Object detection, Object classification, Neural network*

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Using social media as an important channel for e-commerce enterprises to achieve customer's satisfaction, loyalty and trust

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ABSTRACT

Customer's loyalty, satisfaction, and trust are well-known concepts and extensive research was done in the field of e-commerce to study such terms. However, in the era of deploying social media, many e-commerce enterprises are not enough aware of using such new technology for building strong, effective, and beneficial relationships with their customers to gain their satisfaction, trust, and loyalty. Hence, this research offers a valuable opportunity for e-commerce businesses by implementing many tools and strategies and proposes a framework to establish customer's satisfaction, trust, and loyalty.

Keywords: *Social media, loyalty, satisfaction, trust, Word of Mouth*

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Geçirimsiz Yüzeylerden Yağmur Suyu Hasadı Üzerine Optimizasyon Çalışması

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ÖZET

Tüm dünyada artan nüfus, genişleyen şehir yaşamı ve küresel iklim değişikliği gibi çeşitli çevresel sorunların ortaya çıkmasına sebebiyet vermektedir. Bu sorunlardan en büyüğü ise su kıtlığı tehlikesidir. Son yıllarda yeraltı su seviyelerinde önemli derecede düşüş gözlemlenmiştir. Günümüzde suyun sürdürülebilir kullanımı için uygulanmakta olan farklı yöntemler mevcuttur ve Yağmur Suyu Hasadı (YSH), bu yöntemlerden biridir. Hemen hemen her alanda kullanılabilir ve karlı bir stratejidir. Bu çalışmada, sürdürülebilir su kullanımının artması, kuraklığın önlenmesi ve hidrolojik dengenin korunmasına katkı sağlamak amacıyla geçirimsiz yüzeylerden toplanacak yağmur suyu ile yeraltı sularının beslenmesi amaçlanmıştır. Bu amaç doğrultusunda öncelikle yüksek geçirimsiz yüzey alanına sahip olan bölge seçimi yapılmış ve uygulamanın pilot şehir olarak seçilen Eskişehir ili sınırları içerisindeki 1. Organize Sanayi Bölgesinde gerçekleştirilmesine karar verilmiştir. 1. Organize Sanayi Bölgesi ve çevresinde kuyuların kurulacağı en uygun bölgelerin seçimi için Coğrafi Bilgi Sistemleri (CBS)'nden yararlanılmıştır. Öncelikle uzmanlar yardımı ile kuyu yeri seçimini etkileyecek ölçütler belirlenmiş ve Çok Ölçütlü Karar Verme (ÇÖKV) yöntemi olan Analitik Hiyerarşi Süreci (AHP) ile bu ölçütlerin ağırlıklandırılması yapılmıştır. Sonrasında her ölçüt için haritalandırma çalışması ve bu haritalar üzerinde ağırlıklı ölçütlere göre puanlamalar yapılmıştır. Puanlı haritalar kullanılarak, QGIS programı yardımıyla uygun yerler hesaplanmıştır. Çalışma sonunda bir Hedef Programlama Matematiksel Modeli önerisinde bulunulmuştur.

Keywords: sürdürülebilirlik, çok ölçütlü karar verme, analitik hiyerarşi süreci, yağmur suyu hasadı, coğrafi bilgi sistemleri

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Decision Support System Design for Energy Efficient Home Management

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ABSTRACT

Global climate change and increasing waste consumption have gained importance in recent years. The lack of resources has led to new searches in society, resulting in designing self-sufficient models. The increase in energy demand due to population growth has revealed the problem of ineffective management of energy. To eliminate similar problems, this study adopts the "zero energy" philosophy and cares about user comfort while making energy optimization. It offers customer-specific solutions with the help of the decision support system by evaluating the problem through different alternatives. Ensuring the optimization of energy costs through the use and storage systems of renewable energy sources in smart homes will become an essential part of the transition to smart cities. In the study, exact and heuristic algorithms are used simultaneously. A solution is also obtained with heuristic algorithms using the Python language. In the first stage of the study, the devices were classified, and the base case formed with six device types according to their categories. The study's contribution in the first stage is the creation of a multiobjective energy optimization model.

It is thought that positioning the green smart home model, which can be used for different purposes, with clustering algorithms will also contribute to urban planning.

Keywords: *Green-Smart home, HEMS, multiobjective optimization, renewable energy, sustainability*

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The radiation therapy importance in breast cancer

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ABSTRACT

Breast cancer is one of the most frequently diagnosed women cancers. Currently, the treatment of this cancer is based on comprehensive therapy, including surgery, chemotherapy, targeted therapy, hormonotherapy and radiation therapy. This later is most frequently used as Three-Dimensional Conformal RT (3D-CRT), which involves opposing tangential fields to the entire breast. However, it is associated with many side reactions in adjacent organs (OAR), including the heart, lungs, lateral breast, skin, and brachial plexus. This study aim is to assess and compare 12 patients with left and right breast cancer. They were treated by means of a 3D conformal RT in two different positions (ablation of the breast and breast in place) and using two treatment plans: 4 MV beam and 6 MV one, in the “Centre Anti Cancer” (CHUC Constantine Algeria). The mean D95%, and homogeneity index for PTV; mean dose and max doses for the heart; the V20% for the left and the right lungs dosimetric parameters were obtained. In order to ensure the best treatment quality and the best OAR protection, all retrospective study values have been analysed and compared to the normal tissue maximum dose tolerance.

Keywords: Breast cancer, 3D-CRT, X-ray, radiotherapy, OAR, dosimetry.

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Evaluation of Natural Radioactivity Levels and Potential Radiological Risks of Granite Samples Used in Algerian Dwellings

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ABSTRACT

Ionizing radiations emitted by natural radionuclides have always existed in building materials which directly affect human beings and can contribute in accumulated dose in long term. The objective of this work was an investigation of natural radioactivity levels associated radiation hazard in commercial granite samples used in Algeria. A gamma ray spectrometry system composed with a high resolution HPGe semi-conductor detector having resolution of 1.11 keV for 214Bi 609 keV line, was used to measure the radioactivity. The gotten spectra were analyzed using the Genie 2000 software dedicated to the processing of gamma spectra. The activity concentrations of primordial radionuclides 226Ra, 232Th and 40K were determined; they ranged from 6.27 to 145.01 Bq/kg with an average concentration value of 34.19 Bq/kg, from 17.34 to 34.38 Bq/kg with a mean concentration value of 24.10 Bq/kg and from 245.95 to 415.26 Bq/kg with an average concentration value of 352.69 Bq/kg, respectively. Radiological hazards parameters and received doses were calculated and compared to the global average values. The results were found to be lower than the worldwide average values. Moreover, a comparison of the obtained values in this study with the literature was made. Further, statistical analyses were performed and discussed for the resulted data.

Keywords: Ionizing radiations, Granite, Natural radioactivity, Gamma spectrometry, HPGe detector.

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Nuclear structure investigation of even-even proton rich nuclei in vicinity of rp- process path

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ABSTRACT

We investigate even–even nuclei in the vicinity of rp-process waiting point (WP) within the frame work of NushellX@MSU nuclear shell model code. These nuclides are found along the proton-rich side via rapid proton capture rp-process. Typical time scale of this process is about ~ 100 s and WP half-lives are roughly in the same order of magnitude and hence determine the time scale of the nucleosynthesis process and isotopic abundances. Consequently, the knowledge of their spectroscopic properties and their decay modes permits to simulate and modelling the astrophysical explosive phenomena.

This study is based on the valence space consisting of proton and neutron orbitals outside of doubly magic core using new single particles energies. The Hamiltonian deduced from Bonn-C potential was introduced assuming mass dependence and the monopole effect between the core and valence nucleons. Our work includes some nuclear properties calculation of nuclei with the same proton and neutron number ($N = Z$) above Calcium region. The obtained results are compared with the available experimental data and discussed in the rp-process conditions.

Keywords: *rp-process, $Z=N$ proton-rich nuclides , NuShellX@MSU Code.*

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Effective microwave absorption in X band of lightweight, robust, and flexible cellulose nanofibers composites

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ABSTRACT

The lightweight, robust, and flexible microwave absorbing materials are interesting to be developed for use in a variety of applications. Cellulose nanofiber (CNF) composites containing carbon nanotubes (CNT) and Fe₃O₄ were prepared by water pickering emulsion followed by vacuum filtering. The microwave absorbing properties of composite films CNF/CNT/ Fe₃O₄ in the X-band (radar) were evaluated. Reflection loss is calculated using the waveguide method with a vector network analyzer. Analysis of the matching layer and thickness of the absorbing composite was carried out to significantly improve the microwave absorption performance. The high microwave absorption performance with a minimum reflection loss of about -31 dB in the effective absorption of the X-band was demonstrated by the CNF composite at a total thickness of 2 mm double layer, which is based on the impedance matching and damping effect of the composite. The combining of dielectric loss and magnetic loss absorber in the CNF and the design of its double-layer structure indicate that the flexibility effectively improves the absorption performance of the microwave. The thermal stability and mechanical properties of the composites were also evaluated using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and universal testing machine (UTM), respectively. The TGA and UTM test showed good stability and good mechanical strength. These results demonstrated that CNF/CNT/Fe₃O₄ composites had great potential as a composite material in the radar-absorbing coating.

Keywords: *Microwave absorption, cellulose nanofiber composites, CNF/CNT/Fe₃O₄ composite*

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Personalized Daily Tour Planning with Mixed-integer Programming

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ABSTRACT

Suppose a city is to be visited and discovered. In that case, the first action is to investigate must-see places, restaurants, prices, distances between places, the time required to visit, weather, places' scores given by other travelers, and opening hours. Travelers make a tour plan according to this investigation. However, researching all these and deciding which places will be visited in which order is challenging and time-consuming. Moreover, internet ads, place recommendations that are not suitable for personal preferences, and fake comments on social media are considered, and this decision process can become even more difficult. Accordingly, this study presents a mixed-integer mathematical model that plans the daily tour route for individual travelers. The objective function of this model is to maximize the total score obtained from places in the daily route. Besides, this model considers parameters about travelers' preferences and places. Parameters about places are opening and closing hours of the places,

- the score of places,
- category of places

parameters about travelers' preferences are:

- Categories of interest.
- The start time of the tour.
- Time allotted for the tour.
- Start and endpoints of the tour.

The data about places are obtained from Tripadvisor and GoogleMaps by web scraping method, and the data about travelers are gathered from users via the user interface. We conducted several computational studies based on the real-life data of Eskişehir city and discussed the results.

Keywords: *Tourism, Tourist trip design, mixed-integer programming*

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A comparative and systematic study: A review of radon exposure situation in Kosovo

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ABSTRACT

In this study radon (^{222}Rn) activity concentration has been surveyed in different zones of Kosovo in dwellings, workplaces and schools. The radon (^{222}Rn) activity concentration has been measured with the aim to complement the national radon survey and to compare the results with other countries.

The main active method for indoor radon measurement was direct sampling in alpha scintillation cells associated with continuous method, Alpha GUARD radon monitor. But in cases with an increased instantaneous and continuous radon concentrations the additional method of track-etch detectors were applied.

Radon activity concentration in different zones of dwellings ranged from 24 Bq m⁻³ to 868 Bq m⁻³ while, the resulted annual effective doses, from 0.36 to 6.41 mSv y⁻¹.

Radon activity concentrations and the resulting annual effective doses are higher than in some other locations investigated before in Kosovo, and also higher than at several places in the neighboring and other countries. The national limit (adopted from ICRP 65) of 200 Bq m⁻³ for new buildings was exceeded in some houses, workplaces and schools and in some of them also the national limit (adopted from ICRP 65) of 400 Bq m⁻³ for old buildings was exceeded. The impact of lignite-fired power plants on indoor radon concentration has not been observed. Also no impact of depleted uranium on radon levels has been observed.

With these results the radon situation in Kosovo has been upgraded. They have also contributed to fill in the missing data in the European radon map for these zones.

Keywords: radon, review, exposure

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A systematic study: Different factors of radon exposure in workplaces in Kosovo

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ABSTRACT

Exposure to radon and radon decay products at home and at workplaces constitutes one of the greatest and perhaps the greatest risk from ionizing radiation. In this study, radon activity concentrations were surveyed in different workplaces as mines, caves, and in thermal spas of Kosovo.

The main active method for indoor radon measurement was direct sampling in alpha scintillation cells associated with Alpha GUARD radon monitor continuous method and track-etch detectors exposure.

At two points in Gadime cave, values of Rn concentrations higher than 1700 Bq m⁻³ were observed. High values of radon activity concentrations were found also in mines and underground workplaces other than mines.

The indoor air radon concentrations in workrooms, baths, and pools in spas only in one case exceeded 500 Bq m⁻³, although in thermal water, spring water and in the water of baths/pools were found to be 23 Bq l⁻¹ to 314 Bq l⁻¹, 13 Bq l⁻¹ to 270 Bq l⁻¹, 25 Bq l⁻¹ to 108 Bq l⁻¹ and 16 Bq l⁻¹ to 67 Bq l⁻¹ in taps water.

The radon activity concentrations in workplaces are found to be lower than the values reported in the literature in neighbor countries. With these results the radon situation in Kosovo has been upgraded. They have also contributed to fill in the missing data in the European radon map for these zones.

Keywords: radon, mines, spas, caves

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O_52

A=96 proton rich nuclei and Gamow-Teller decay properties

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ABSTRACT

A=96 isotopes, situated near proton drip line, nuclear structure study provides relevant information about nuclear interaction for such exotic nuclei. Due to their existence in the astrophysical rp-process path, these isobars present good candidates for the investigation of the astrophysical elements nucleosynthesis. In this context, the work carried out within the framework of this study is based on the nuclear structure and Gamow-Teller decay calculations of A=96 isobars, starting from ⁹⁶Cd rp-process waiting point. The calculations are carried out in the framework of nuclear shell model using NuShellX@MSU code in ¹⁰⁰Sn doubly magic mass region. Based on the sn100pn interaction, we have performed some modifications considering the region and the mass effects to introduce the used effective interaction. The obtained results have been compared to the available experimental data.

Keywords: A=96 isobars, Nuclear structure, Gamow-Teller decay, Proton rich nuclei, NuShellX@MSU code

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β^+ decay nuclear properties of A=80 isobars

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ABSTRACT

The spectroscopic estimation properties of proton-rich nuclides in the A=80 mass region is needed for the understanding of rp-process path and experimental exploration of the nuclear landscape. In order to evaluate some spectroscopic properties of A=80 Zirconium isotopes Gamow-Teller β decay, we have performed shell model calculations by means of NushellX@MSU nuclear structure code. The used valence space consists of the proton and neutron orbitals outside of a doubly magic core using new single particles energies. The study is based on the core polarisation investigation and the effective interaction used in this region taking into account the nuclear monopole effect. Our calculations include energy spectra and Gamow-Teller reduced transitions probabilities of A=80 isobars. The obtained results are then compared with the available experimental data.

Keywords: A=80 Isobarsi, β decay, NuShellX@MSU nuclear code.

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β^+ decay of A=97 proton rich isobars in 100Sn mass region

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ABSTRACT

Nuclei lie in rp-process path study offers important information for nuclear structure in limit condition. These systems located near proton drip line provides the opportunity to test nuclear models. In this context, the work carried out within the framework of this study is based on the nuclear structure and Gamow-Teller decay calculations of A=97 isobars in the astrophysical path. The calculations are carried out in the framework of nuclear shell model using NuShellX@MSU code in 100Sn doubly magic mass region. Considering nuclear similarity and mass effect, we have performed some modifications based on the sn100pn interaction to introduce the used effective interaction. The obtained results have been compared to the available experimental data.

Keywords: A=97 isobars, Nuclear structure, Gamow-Teller decay, 100Sn mass region, NuShellX@MSU code

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Dosimetric study in radiationtherapy (prostate cancer treatment)

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ABSTRACT

Cancer is a major public health problem. Treatments can be systemic or locoregional. In the latter case, the treatment technique plays an important role in making it possible to specify the tumor location. The radiotherapy goal is to deliver a curative radiation dose to the target volume while sparing nearby organs at risk (OAR). Determining the precise location of this target volume as well as the OARs make it possible to define the position and power of the irradiation beams to be used. In this work, we used clinical challenges of 12 prostate cancer cases.

The various treatments results were evaluated using a dosimetric study. According to the therapeutic regimen recommended by the Oncological Radiotherapy French Society (SFRO), the total 74 Gy dose assigned to these prostate cancer patients was divided into 37 fractions. Several interesting results can be noted in our study. The dose constraints, concerning the target volume and the organs at risk, were respected. However, qualitative and quantitative analyzes of the results show optimal target volume coverage only in the 4 cases.

Keywords: *prostate, treatment cancer, radiationtherapy, RX.*

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O_56

Influence of some Parameters on the QCD Phase Diagram within the MIT Bag Model

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ABSTRACT

We investigate, in the present work, the QCD phase diagram in the μ -T plane within the MIT Bag Model. We derive the equations of state of the hadronic gas phase consisting of pions and the Quark-Gluon Plasma (QGP) phase containing gluons and up and down quarks with their antiquarks. We consider several cases of massless pions and massless quarks, massive pions and massless quarks and massive particles in the two phases, and we examine the effect of the mass on deconfinement phase transition parameters (T_c , μ_c), especially at extreme conditions of temperature T and chemical potential μ . We also examine the influence of different terms of the density of states of quarks and gluons, given by the Multiple Reflexion Expansion (MRE) approximation, used in the calculation of the partition functions, on the transition parameters.

Keywords: *Quark-Gluon Plasma, Deconfinement phase transition, Phase diagram, Mass effect*

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O_57

Single particle evolution along N=51 isotones

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ABSTRACT

Neutron-rich ^{78}Ni doubly magic nucleus and its neighbours provide an excellent topic to test the theoretical nuclear models, due to the limited experimental data about it.

In this regard, the present work is concerned with the study of the neutron single energies out of its doubly closed shell situated at N=50, to achieve that, we study the evolution of experimental energies states for N=51 isotones.

In addition we realised calculation using the Hartree-Fock method employing the Skyrme potential SK20-Skx for the studied isotones as a comparison.

Keywords: *Single particle energies, Doubly magic ^{78}Ni , NuShellX@MSU code, Skyrme force potential*

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European Union (EU) Hydrogen Energy Policy and Auto Industry

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ABSTRACT

As part of its industrial policy, the European Commission adopted a hydrogen strategy for a climate-neutral Europe by 2050 in July 2020. Yet, most European automakers are skeptical about hydrogen-ran passenger cars, unlike their Japanese and South Korean counterparts' strong support. This article examines this puzzle from a Post Keynesian economics perspective. While the first section introduces the topic and offers a brief literature review, the second section outlines the theoretical perspective, followed by the hydrogen energy policies of the EU in the third section. The fourth section investigates the business strategies of European carmakers and the factors behind their skepticism toward hydrogen fuel-cell cars. The fifth and last section summarizes the findings as a way of conclusion.

Keywords: *Hydrogen energy, European Union, Auto Industry*

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Radiation Shielding Test of PbO added Composite

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ABSTRACT

Radiation has been used for many years in many different fields and due to its harmful effect shielding has been important for researcher. There have been many different works in order to develop new shielding materials.

In this work composite materials has been developed adding into PbO and gamma shielding properties has been measured. The measurements were done using NaI(Tl) detector system and some gamma sources.

Keywords: *gamma radiation, NaI(Tl) detector, composite*

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Prediction of Compressive Strength of Concrete in Palestinian Using Machine Learning Techniques

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ABSTRACT

In construction fields, one of the conventional approaches for quality control of the concrete is to use the compressive strength (CS) of laboratory samples, This Process requires time to reach its maximum resistance, therefore, the results of its tests are far from being immediate, so, it is important to have a compression resistance prediction model through Artificial Intelligence (AI) approaches. Machine Learning (ML) techniques can classify the CS of concrete by using the concrete mixture as input data for the ML methods to predict the CS of concrete.

In this research, the datasets were collected from Palestinian laboratories and concrete factories in 7 Palestinian governorates. The dataset consists of 715 samples which consist of eight inputs features: coarse aggregate, fine aggregate, cement, water, w/c ratio, age, location, and superplasticizer.

Different ML techniques were used to classify the compressive strength of concrete, where three methods were used: Multilayer Feed Forward Neural Networks (MLPNNs), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Ensemble Algorithm. The accuracy results were 93.5%, 80.4% and 90.2% respectively for B200 concrete, and the classification results for B250 concrete were 90.0%, 66.5% and 75.5% respectively. For B300 concrete, the classification results were 93.3%, 68.3% and 79.2% respectively.

The classification results were 90.6%, 83.3% and 85.6% respectively for B350 concrete, and the classification results were 90.0%, 80.6% and 78.6% respectively for B400 concrete. The results showed that the MLPNNs using Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm are the most accurate for each type of concrete.

Keywords: Concrete compressive strength, predication, Machine Learning

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Design and Characterization of Tungsten Trioxide Devices

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ABSTRACT

Tungsten trioxide (WO₃) / lithium (Li) / Tungsten trioxide (WO₃) thin films were designed and fabricated. A thin layer of 100 nm Li were inserted between two 500 nm of WO₃. Thin film layers are coated by thermal evaporation technique under a vacuum pressure of 10-5 mbar using VCM 300 evaporation system. The Structural properties of the device is investigated by using X-Ray Rigaku miniflex 600 diffractometer. The electrical characterization which were carried out by the 4291B Agilent impedance analyzer which have shown that; stacked layers of tungsten oxide comprising Li nano-sheets can perform as microwave resonators. Resonance anti-resonance phenomena is observed in the samples. Moreover, the capacitance spectra which we studied in the frequency domain of 0.01-1.8 GHz have shown the dominants of negative capacitance effect. This effect is beneficial for parasitic capacitance cancellation and noise reduction in electronic circuits. Furthermore, the WO₃/Li/WO₃ device seems to be used in application as thin film MOSFET that can be used digital and analog circuits.

Keywords: Negative capacitance, Tungsten trioxide, microwave resonators

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Synthesis, characterizations and electrical properties of novel azo-chalcone derivative

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ABSTRACT

Chalcones, as one of the well-known class of organic compounds which are mostly present in flavonoids [1]. Chemically, they are open chain of flavonoids consisting two aromatic rings having diverse array of substitutes linked by α , β -unsaturated carbonyl groups. Chalcones possess conjugated double bonds and a completely delocalized π -electron system on both benzene rings [2]. Because of the ketovinyl group (-CO-CH=CH-) and p-conjugated bridges in chalcones and their analogs, they exhibit numerous chemical and physical properties, for instance optical and fluorescence properties [3,4] and electric properties. Chalcones have attracted much attention for several decades due to their potential technological application in fields of optical and photochemical sensors. Azo dyes have become interesting groups in photophysical applications due to the shift of their absorption bands to visible wavelengths. shows that such materials have photoconductive properties and can be used in both solar cell and photodiode applications.

In this study a novel azo-chalcone derivative has been synthesized by the reaction of amino-chalcone and phenol in presence of NaNO₂. The synthesized compound was characterized by FT-IR, ¹H NMR, and ¹³C-NMR spectroscopic techniques.

The dielectric and electrical properties of novel azo-chalcone derivative were investigated as a function of frequency and temperature in the frequency range of 1–200 kHz. It is clearly seen that the dielectric constant decreases with increasing frequency values at constant temperatures. It is also possible to see that the dielectric constant increases with increasing temperature values. It has been observed that the dielectric constant and dielectric loss decrease as the frequency increases and remain constant at higher frequency values

Keywords: Azo-chalcone, Synthesis, Electrical properties

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Performance of ferrocement slabs at elevated temperature

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ABSTRACT

Ferrocement is an excellent construction material due to its mechanical properties, ease of construction, and economical aspects. It also had excellent tensile strength, fire resistance, lightness and resistance to cracking. The primary goal of this work is to investigate the thermogravimetric analysis, surface performance, and flexural properties of ferrocement slabs at elevated temperature. Three types of samples were used-1.25% reinforcement (Mesh Opening-12.5 mm), 2.5% reinforcement (Mesh Opening-12.5 mm) and 1.25% reinforcement (Mesh Opening-33.25 mm). The slabs were heated up to 500°C in a furnace. In the thermogravimetric analysis, the ferrocement slabs having a lower percentage of reinforcement had lost more weight than slabs having a higher percentage of reinforcement. Controlled samples had better flexure performance than the heated samples. Of the heated samples, those that had a higher percentage of reinforcement had better flexure strength than the samples that had a lower percentage of reinforcement. But with the increase of temperature, the difference of flexural strength in higher and lower percentage of reinforcement were minimized and nearly similar at very high temperature. In terms of surface cracking, lower percentage of reinforcement of small mesh opening had generated higher cracking areas than the other types. And samples having higher percentage of reinforcement and samples having lower percentage of reinforcement of large mesh opening showed nearly similar kind of performance.

Keywords: *Ferrocement, Thermogravimetric analysis, Surface performance, Flexural properties, wire mesh*

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Ensemble learning based machine learning models for predictive maintenance

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ABSTRACT

Predictive maintenance is an approach that uses data collected from sensors on machines to predict machine failure before a fault occurs. Predicting failure allows for machine maintenance to be planned ahead of time. Unexpected production halts can thus be prevented. Machine failures are typically predicted using machine learning algorithms through data acquired from sensors. Using the AI4I 2020 Predictive Maintenance Dataset, an effort was made to construct a fault detection system in this study. To predict machine failures with high accuracy, ensemble learning models based on voting and bagging methods, which includes different machine learning algorithms, are proposed. These machine learning algorithms are Support Vector Machines, K-Nearest Neighbor, Logistic Regression and Decision Trees. For the considered dataset, the ensemble learning-based models built in the study can predict machine breakdowns faults with a 99% accuracy.

Keywords: *Predictive Maintenance, Machine Failure, Ensemble Learning, Machine Learning.*

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Mikro Kanal Akışına Sahip Evaporatörün Yenilikçi R1234yf Gazı ile Farklı Operatif Şartlar ve Kanal Uzunluklarında Faz Dönüşümü Mekanizmasının Nümerik İncelenmesi

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ÖZET

Soğutucu akışkanlar her ne kadar günlük hayatımızdaki cihazlarda sıklıkla kullanılıyor olsa da, zamanla doğaya verdiği yıkıcı etki anlaşılmış ve bu konuda önlemler alınmaya başlanmıştır. R134a gibi gazlar hala yaygın olarak kullanılmasına karşın yüksek GWP (Global Warming Potential) değerlerinden dolayı benzer ısıl performansı gösterecek fakat daha düşük GWP değeri ile doğaya en az zararı verecek R1234yf gibi gazlar popüler hale gelmiştir.

Gerçekleştirilen çalışmada mikro akışa sahip bir evaporatörün farklı operatif ve farklı kanal uzunluklarında R1234yf gazı ile olan faz dönüşümü mekanizmasının karakteristiği nümerik olarak incelenmiştir.

Çalışma ilk olarak R1234yf gazının ANSYS Fluent yazılımının malzeme veri tabanına tanımlanması ile başlamıştır. Bu süreçte her iki faz ayrı birer malzeme olarak ele alınmıştır. Özgül ısı, ısıl iletkenlik, viskozite gibi termodinamik özellikler sıcaklığa bağlı polinom fonksiyonu olarak tanımlandığı çalışmada malzeme yoğunluk değişimi ise Peng-Robinson hal denklemi ile sağlanmıştır. Son olarak ise basınç-sıcaklık doyma eğrisi değerleri tablo olarak faz dönüşüm koşulu olarak tanımlanmıştır.

Giriş koşulları %100 sıvı olacak şekilde, çıkışta ise %100 sıvı ve %100 buhar koşullarında olacak şekilde parametrik değişken seçimleri yapılmıştır. Bu doğrultuda, 264,15 ve 290,0 K arasında değişen 4 farklı sabit evaporatör yüzey sıcaklığı, 0,15 ve 0,3 m/s arasında değişen, uniform, hız girişi değerine karşılık olan 4 farklı R1234yf giriş debisi ve sabit çıkış basıncı koşullarında 209 ve 3344 mm arasında değişen 3 farklı uzunlukta (1 boy uzunluk, 4 boy uzunluk ve 16 boy uzunluk) olan evaporatördeki çıkış kurulum dereceleri karşılaştırılmıştır. Kurulum derecesi dışında giriş-çıkış entalpi farkları incelenmiş, evaporatör akış kesiti boyunca, sıcaklık, basınç ve kurulum derecesi dağılımları görselleştirilmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Mikro Kanal Akışı, Evaporatör, Faz Değişimi, Buharlaştırma, R1234yf, Hesaplamalı Akışkanlar Dinamiği, ANSYS Fluent

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Optimization of Process Parameters of Local Area Network (LAN) Cables

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ABSTRACT

Local Area Network (LAN) is the term used for the smallest network structure created by more than one computer. Many cables structure is used in data transmission in the LAN system. The most used LAN cable class is CAT 6 and used in telephone lines, in-home network, and in-office network. The potential bandwidth of CAT6 cable is 1000 Mbps, the transfer time for 1 terabyte is 3 hours, the minimum operating frequency is 250 Mhz, and the maximum operating frequency is 500 Mhz. LAN cable production line starts with copper wire drawing, then continues with annealing, insulating coating and cooling. In this study, the effects of production parameters on tensile strength, percent elongation, diameter and eccentricity were investigated. A: Line Speed (m/min), B: Annealer Current (A) and C: Extruder Heat Profiles (°C) were chosen as production parameters. Two levels were defined for each parameter and the L8 experiment table, which is a full factorial experimental design, was used. For each experiment, the strength values were measured off-line, and the geometric values were automatically measured on-line systems. As a results of experimental analysis and statistical studies, it has been determined that the selected input experimental parameters have a significant effect on tensile strength and percent elongation but have little effect on geometric values. With future studies, the performance of the produced cable in terms of data transmission can be examined and new experimental studies can be carried out in which other production parameters are also evaluated.

Keywords: Local Area Network (LAN), Cat6 Cables, Optimization, Experimental Design

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Radiation dose Parameters for Environmental sample

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ABSTRACT

Radiation has existed since the creation of universe so called Big-Bang and since then we are exposed to this radiation in different rate in different locations. It is important to know this natural radiation as it will be possible to estimate if any changes/contaminations happened. This requires monitoring of radiation and obtaining some dose parameters. In this work radiation dose have been measured in Konya region and radiation parameters extracted for some samples collected environment.

Keywords: *Radiation dose, Environmental samples, radiation effect*

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O_68

A Study of Smart Ports by Cargo Handling in Antwerp Port

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ABSTRACT

And the most popular maritime transportation type of that for non-bulk cargoes is inter modal transportation with containers.

It can be claimed that the future way of maritime transportation will be dominated by artificial intelligence. To decrease the share of human error in accidents and to meet the increasing cargo capacity, cargo handling operations at container terminals are begun to be automatized. In this study, Port of Antwerp example is examined. Its figures, peculiarities and systems in the sense of artificial intelligence and automatization were stated. Lastly, how to adapt this to Turkish ports is discussed. Questions like “Needed why?” and “Where to start?” is answered.

Consequently, even if it is under the threat of hacking; due to their consistent, sustainable, and fast character, automatic cargo handling systems with artificial intelligence seems as the prevalent solution to face with all problems of growing global trade.

Keywords: *AI, Intelligent transportation, Smart ports*

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Radium equivalent dose from Natural Radiation Measurement

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ABSTRACT

A large part of the total radiation exposure of living beings is due to natural source radiation. Natural radionuclides such as ⁴⁰K, ²²⁶Ra and ²³²Th in the environment are found in different proportions in water, air, soil and sediment. In particular, the most determining factors of natural background radiation in environmental materials such as stone, soil, sand are the activity concentrations of ⁴⁰K, ²²⁶Ra and ²³²Th natural radionuclides. The concentration of radionuclides in these materials is important for finding the source of natural radioactivity, determining environmental effects and assessing radiation risks. The various radiation hazard indexes can calculate using the conversion factors given in UNSCEAR reports and natural radionuclide concentrations to determine health risks. In this study, the radium equivalent activity (Raeq) values of sand samples collected from some beaches in the İstanbul-Şişli region were determined. The results obtained were compared with the world averages.

Keywords: Natural radionuclides, radium equivalent activity, sand samples, UNSCEAR

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Monte Carlo Approaches for Radiation Shielding

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ABSTRACT

As the radiation shielding is important for especially radiation workers, it is important to predict radiation shielding properties of any materials used in radiation protection purposes. In order to get radiation shielding properties surely measurement is a vital way, but it may not be always possible. In this case simulation becomes important and researcher may use it. In this work some monte carlo methods detailed and results presented.

Keywords: radiation shielding, Monte Carlo, gamma rays

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How much radiation may be shielded by a Wood ?

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ABSTRACT

Radiation shielding has been one of the most popular topics in scientific research as the radiation may effect human. Using many different types of materials it has been tested and tried to be developed new alternative materials. On the other hand wood and wood based materials is important and thus in this study, the gamma ray shielding properties of wood samples have been measured.

Keywords: wood, radiation, gamma rays

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Production of modified bentonite-boron carbide ceramics for neutron radiation shielding

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ABSTRACT

In this study, Na-Bentonite was modified with a barium salts to make cation exchange. Ba bentonite and boron carbide powders were mixed and pressed in different proportions. The sintering temperature of each mixture was determined by using a heat microscope. The mixture was sintered at different temperatures. Neutron radiation shielding of modified bentonite-boron carbide ceramics was investigated. It was observed that neutron radiation protection decreased as the Barium bentonite contribution to modified bentonite-boron carbide ceramic increased.

Keywords: Boron carbide, Modified Bentonite, Radiation Shielding, neutron radiation

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O_75

Demand Forecasting with Simple Linear Regression, Multiple Linear Regression and Artificial Neural Networks in a Gas Distribution Company

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ABSTRACT

Due to its efficient, reliable, and flexible structure, natural gas is an important energy source in Turkey. In addition, it has become widespread rapidly due to its ease of use and clean energy. Despite its rapid spread, Turkey is dependent on foreign natural gas. Gas distribution companies should be cautious while supplying gas because this situation significantly affects economic data. It should know its users' profiles, make accurate predictions, and agree with gas suppliers. In this way, it can contribute to the economic data of the country by preventing the additional costs that may occur. Natural gas estimation is made not only in Turkey but worldwide. The widespread use of natural gas has made it an important energy source for the world. Therefore, in this study, natural gas consumption data of a province was tried to be estimated. This study estimated the natural gas consumption amount for the next period using the natural gas consumption data for the first six months of 2019. First, daily estimations were made with simple linear regression and multiple regression models, which are statistical estimation methods. Then, natural gas estimations were made with artificial neural networks, and the results were compared.

Keywords: *Artificial neural network, Regression model, Simple linear regression*

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O_76

Prediction of Electricity Demand in Turkey with Artificial Neural Networks and Interface Development with Python

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ABSTRACT

The demand for electrical energy is increasing daily with the increase in its population, and other countries besides Turkey are evaluating the changes and determining their future policies. Electric consumption per capita is one of the most critical parameters in determining countries' development levels. In deciding this, the estimation of electrical energy demands is made. This study estimated the electricity demand in Turkey, and the data between 1960 and 2019 was used. Artificial Neural Networks demand forecasting method has been developed using PYTHON programming language. Thanks to the interface designed in the Python program, users are provided with faster and easier demand forecasts.

Keywords: *Demand Forecasting, Electricity Demand, Artificial Neural Networks, Interface Design*

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